

Extreme Food Risk Analytics

D6.2.3: Integrated toolset for multiplying impact

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
Abbreviation / Term	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BM	Business Model
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
EU	European Union
GMP	Good Manufacturing Practices
HACCP	Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points
HPC	High Performance Computing
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IMF	International Monetary Fund
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NLU	Natural Language Understanding
PAPs	Processed Animal Proteins
R&D	Research and Development
UVP	Unique Value Proposition
WP	Work Package
YoY	Year over Year

Executive Summary

The present report constitutes the final strategic and sustainability assessment of the EFRA project, delivered within the Horizon Europe framework. It consolidates the outcomes achieved over the full project lifecycle and presents a comprehensive overview of how EFRA has advanced the state of the art in food safety through the application of predictive analytics and artificial intelligence (AI). The document reflects the maturity of the project results and their readiness for exploitation, uptake, and long-term sustainability.

The report provides an integrated description of the EFRA use cases developed and validated during the project, demonstrating the technical robustness and practical relevance of the EFRA platform. These include AI-driven predictive analytics for salmonella risk in poultry farming, advanced pest detection and early-warning systems, automated regulatory and compliance analysis, and complementary analytical services. Collectively, the use cases illustrate how EFRA enables data-driven decision-making across the food safety value chain, supporting both risk prevention and regulatory compliance in real-world operational environments.

A core element of the report is the finalised Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management framework, which ensures the protection, valorisation, and sustainable use of the innovative assets generated by the consortium. The document outlines the processes established to identify background and foreground IP, define ownership and access rights, and support exploitation pathways for project results. This structured approach underpins the long-term competitiveness of EFRA in a rapidly evolving, data-intensive food safety landscape. In addition, the report summarises the key conclusions of the market analyses conducted during the project, building on earlier deliverables, and confirms the strong growth potential of data-driven food safety solutions. These findings position EFRA as a credible and timely response to emerging market needs.

The report also presents the final version of the EFRA Business Models Playbook, which synthesises lessons learned and provides practical guidance for the deployment of sustainable and scalable business models for both the EFRA platform and its individual use cases. The playbook aligns technological innovation with market demand and stakeholder expectations, thereby supporting post-project exploitation and long-term value creation. Complementing this, the report details the consolidated sustainability plan, defining organisational, technical, and financial strategies to ensure continuity of the platform and its services beyond the project's end. The plan demonstrates the consortium's commitment to responsible innovation and proactive risk management.

Furthermore, the report documents the final exploitation strategy and performance indicators developed to maximise the impact, visibility, and usability of EFRA results in both commercial and non-commercial contexts. Over the course of the project, the portfolio of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) expanded from three to eight, reflecting the growing maturity and breadth of EFRA innovations. These include, among others, a RoBERTa-based web page classification tool and customised AI predictive models for mycotoxin risk assessment. Each KER is associated with a clearly defined Unique Value Proposition, articulating its relevance for target stakeholders and reinforcing EFRA's contribution to AI-enabled food risk management.

Finally, the report highlights the project's strategic evolution in business model development through the adoption of the DSSC Collaborative Business Model Development Tool. This transition from the traditional Business Model Canvas reflects EFRA's engagement with the complexities of data-driven ecosystems, data spaces, and platform-based services. The selected approach enables a more accurate representation of data governance, monetisation mechanisms, and regulatory compliance requirements, thereby strengthening EFRA's readiness for sustainable operation in the European data economy.

1. Requirements

This final deliverable (D6.2.3), produced within *Task 6.4 “EFRA Sustainability Plan & Business Models”* under *WP6 “Generating Impact”*, consolidates the completed integrated toolset designed to maximise EFRA’s long-term impact across the European data and food safety ecosystems. Building on the foundations established in D6.2.1 and refined in D6.2.2, this final version presents the mature, validated, and fully integrated framework that will guide EFRA’s post-project continuity.

D6.2.3 fulfils three core objectives:

1. Final validation of EFRA’s IPR management system, confirming ownership, protection, and exploitation pathways for all project-generated intellectual property, including new assets identified during the final project period.
2. Delivery of the fully developed business model for the EFRA platform, using the data-space-oriented business model tool to reflect market trends, regulatory developments, and operational insights gained through real-life testing of EFRA’s use cases.
3. Completion of the EFRA Sustainability Plan, detailing the concrete measures, governance structures, resource pathways, and collaboration mechanisms required to ensure long-term uptake of EFRA solutions across the EU food supply chain and data space ecosystem.

Serving as the definitive reference document for all exploitation and sustainability activities, D6.2.3 incorporates the full set of insights, feedback, and performance evidence gathered during demonstrations and validation activities. The document confirms the readiness of EFRA’s business model, the robustness of its IPR strategy, and the operational viability of its sustainability plan.

Structured across a coherent set of ten chapters, the deliverable outlines the final logic, strategic positioning, and implementation framework for durable integration of EFRA’s results. It ensures that the platform, its associated services, and its Key Exploitable Results can continue to generate value, support innovation, and contribute to safer, more resilient food systems across Europe beyond the end of the project.

2. EFRA'S Use Cases and technical capabilities

The EFRA Platform and its associated components have been validated through four diverse use cases that collectively demonstrate the breadth of EFRA's technical capabilities in food risk prediction, data integration, federated learning, and large-scale data crawling and mining. Across all use cases, EFRA technologies were deployed under real operational conditions, enabling continuous optimisation of AI models and data-processing modules using both public datasets from the EFRA Data Hub and confidential datasets available only at the premises of participating organisations.

Use Case #1 applied EFRA's full two-level AI training approach. At the first level, suitable AI models were pretrained using public datasets and the computational resources of the EFRA High-Performance Computing infrastructure. At the second level, these models were further trained on site through a privacy-preserving, edge-based process, using confidential datasets and local computing resources provided by Moy Park. Additional participants were then engaged to evaluate federated learning, where the same model circulated across multiple premises and was incrementally improved using each participant's private data. This ensured that sensitive information remained local while still contributing to a shared, more accurate model.

Use Case #2 followed a different configuration. AGRIVI's pest-prediction scenario relied directly on proprietary scouting, weather, and agronomic datasets, without the need for public-data pretraining or federated learning. The focus was on validating and enhancing AGRIVI's existing pest-prediction algorithm using real-world data collected from farmers and participating primary producers, demonstrating how EFRA components can strengthen domain-specific decision-support systems.

Use Case #3 demonstrated the collaborative potential of the EFRA Data & Analytics Marketplace, where users can upload new datasets, data crawlers, AI models, and natural-language-understanding micro-modules. The Marketplace centrally manages crawling workloads through the EFRA Green Cloud HPC infrastructure, prioritising tasks based on the popularity and relevance of each data source. This approach reduces redundant crawling, lowers computational and energy costs, and enables the integration of new data types into AI models with minimal technical overhead.

Use Case #4 extended EFRA's capabilities into a new domain (mycotoxins in animal feed) showcasing how the Marketplace and EFRA's analytical engines can be applied to additional contexts beyond the original GA. By combining anonymised private datasets with public incident reports, trade flows, and weather indicators, the use case demonstrated how EFRA can support trend forecasting and risk assessment in emerging or under-served areas of food safety.

Across all four use cases, the EFRA Data & Analytics Marketplace establishes a collaborative environment in which organisations active in the food safety digital data economy are encouraged to specialise in particular data sources and contribute their own resources. By enabling the upload of data crawlers, mining software, AI models, and NLU modules, the Marketplace consolidates workloads and executes them efficiently through the EFRA Green Cloud HPC infrastructure. This reduces unnecessary computational and energy consumption while promoting data reuse, interoperability, and cross-stakeholder collaboration.

To further incentivise participation, the EFRA Platform will introduce an intelligent and dynamic monetisation and trading system. Contributors of valuable or insufficiently covered data sources and data types will receive enhanced monetary rewards, which can be used within the internal Marketplace economy to access outputs generated by other crawlers, AI models, NLU modules, or processed datasets. This mechanism supports the creation of a consolidated market for food safety data resources and fosters a sustainable ecosystem in which stakeholders can collaborate while maintaining their specialisation and competitive advantage.

2.1. Use Case #1 - Risks prediction for poultry pathogens

To ensure the safety of primary ingredients and meat products, the presence of specific pathogens in the poultry industry requires continuous monitoring and early detection. In line with the original EFRA GA, this use case focused on supporting Moy Park (as well as other key players in the poultry industry) in transitioning

from traditional pathogen-management practices (e.g., Salmonella) to a more proactive, data-driven approach. The initial ambition was to develop AI-based tools capable of analysing environmental conditions, laboratory test results, incident reports and recalls, and other contextual factors to identify patterns and potential causal drivers of pathogen contamination at poultry farms. This would enable operators to intervene before issues escalate, moving from reactive to predictive risk management.

To achieve this, the project planned to leverage a broad set of existing datasets, including historic pathogen incidents (e.g., Salmonella occurrences) combined with key contextual factors such as weather data (e.g., temperature), incident and recall reports, laboratory test results, production-level farm data, and trade-related production information. Early analytical work also explored correlation analysis to understand how environmental and operational factors may influence pathogen occurrence. In addition, the project aimed to collect detailed poultry production data at flock level, including the timing of flock cycles, mortality rates, and weight-gain rates. These indicators were expected to reveal early behavioural patterns and help estimate the expected number of birds that would successfully grow and reach uniform target weights.

The targeted users for the pilot phase included food safety experts, technical support teams, and farm process managers, with key performance indicators focusing on model accuracy and user satisfaction with decision-support dashboards.

Use case Update

As the project progressed, detailed analysis of the available datasets revealed that pathogen occurrence at farm level is extremely rare, making direct prediction statistically challenging. This rarity, combined with the variability of farm-level operational conditions, highlighted that farms do not follow uniform behavioural patterns. Instead, distinct clusters emerged across mortality rates, weight-gain trajectories, and flock-level performance indicators. These insights guided the evolution of the use case toward tools that provide early warning signals, behavioural pattern detection, and incident-driven forecasting, which are better aligned with the nature of the data and the operational needs of poultry producers. Two operational dashboards were therefore developed and deployed as part of the EFRA platform:

(a) Flock Performance Outlier Detection Dashboard

This dashboard identifies abnormal flock behaviour that may signal elevated pathogen risk or operational issues. It clusters flocks based on mortality and weight-gain patterns, highlights atypical trajectories, and enables users to download detailed flock characteristics for deeper investigation. Users can also input early flock data to assess whether a flock resembles known high-risk outlier patterns, supporting earlier and more targeted interventions.

(b) Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard

This dashboard provides global monitoring and prediction of poultry-related food safety incidents using publicly available regulatory data. It offers historical trend analysis, short- and medium-term forecasts, geographical comparisons, and a 12-month hazard heat map. Integrated with the EFRA Scraping Platform and Timeseries Engine, it supports proactive risk awareness across the poultry supply chain and helps operators anticipate emerging threats.

2.2. Use Case #2 - Food Safety Optimal Pesticides Use

To ensure safe and compliant crop production, farmers must manage pesticide applications in accordance with strict regulatory requirements, including maximum residue limits (MRLs) and country-specific usage rules. In line with the EFRA Grant Agreement, this use case focused on supporting AGRIVI and primary producers in moving from traditional compliance-based pesticide management to a more proactive, data-driven approach. The initial ambition was to develop AI-based tools capable of analysing agro-climatological conditions, weather patterns, soil indicators, farm-level operational data, and regulatory constraints to provide personalised, food-safety-optimal pesticide recommendations. This would help

farmers reduce unnecessary pesticide use, minimise residue risks, and adapt decisions to local micro-climatic and agronomic conditions.

To achieve this, the project planned to leverage a broad set of datasets, including agro-climatological and meteo-climatological data, soil and irrigation indicators, chemical-specific regulatory limits, and best-practice guidelines. These were complemented by publicly available data aggregated in the EFRA Data Hub, such as incident reports, border rejections, laboratory test results, inspection findings, and scientific or expert-driven textual sources processed through EFRA's advanced NLU capabilities. The targeted users included farmers, agronomists, and technical advisors, with the goal of improving prediction accuracy and delivering actionable, farm-specific recommendations.

Use case Update

As the project evolved, the focus of the use case shifted toward enhanced predictive capabilities for pest alarms, building on AGRIVI's existing pest and disease algorithm. The updated approach aimed to improve the accuracy, timing, and contextual relevance of pest predictions by integrating historical scouting data, real-time and forecasted weather conditions, agronomic rules, and additional datasets collected for maize and sunflower crops.

(a) Interactive Decision Tree and Prediction Dashboard

Developed within the AGRIVI Farm Management System, this dashboard supports early identification and forecasting of pest risks. It continuously evaluates environmental thresholds and pest development criteria to generate AI-based pest alerts, informing farmers about:

- which pest is likely to occur,
- where (crop/field) it may appear, and
- when the risk period is expected.

This enhanced capability strengthens AGRIVI's decision-support ecosystem by providing more precise, timely, and crop-specific pest warnings, enabling farmers to take preventive action and optimise pesticide use for improved food safety outcomes.

2.3. Use Case #3 - Informing Regulatory, Decisions with Food Risk Intelligence

The food safety data ecosystem is highly fragmented, with multiple organisations (e.g. food manufacturers), independently extracting information from publicly available sources such as RASFF. This duplication leads to unnecessary computational and energy costs, while the addition of new data sources or formats requires specialised expertise in both domain knowledge and computer science. As a result, no single actor can access the volume and diversity of data needed to train high-performing AI models, limiting the adoption of preventive, intelligence-driven food safety approaches across the industry.

Food safety regulation itself is a complex, multi-stakeholder process that requires timely access to both regulatory texts and emerging food risk intelligence. However, the absence of an integrated solution, capable of combining regulatory data with risk signals, forces compliance teams and authorities to rely on manual interpretation of lengthy, technical documents. In the current state, SGS Digicomply provides extensive regulatory datasets, but users must interpret and summarise these documents themselves, which is time-consuming and resource-intensive.

The envisioned future state, aligned with the EFRA Grant Agreement and early deliverables, includes the development of an Automated Regulatory Analysis & Summarization Module. This module aims to reduce user workload by generating concise summaries and key extracts from complex regulatory texts, improving efficiency and supporting faster decision-making. Key challenges include ensuring accuracy across diverse regulatory formats and languages. Targeted users include product compliance units within food companies and regulators specialising in food safety, with performance indicators focused on summary accuracy, user satisfaction, and time saved in regulatory analysis.

Use case Update

As part of the EFRA demonstrator development, SGS Digicomply delivered two complementary AI-powered tools that directly address the challenges identified in the initial vision: an automated summarisation dashboard and a regulatory citation chatbot.

(a) Regulatory Document Summarisation Dashboard

This module automatically generates concise, high-quality summaries of regulatory documents, enabling users to quickly identify key obligations, requirements, and thematic elements without reading lengthy source texts. Integrated into the SGS Digicomply platform, the tool was refined throughout the project to improve accuracy, readability, and alignment with regulatory language. User interface enhancements further improved accessibility for both technical and non-specialist users.

(b) Regulatory Citation and Compliance Chatbot

In parallel, a conversational chatbot was developed to support interactive exploration of regulatory content. Users can ask natural-language questions and receive contextualised responses, including citations from specific sections of regulatory documents. Operating on the same repository as the summarisation module, the chatbot ensures consistency between summarised content and conversational outputs. Iterative improvements based on stakeholder feedback enhanced both usability and the accuracy of responses.

2.4. Use Case #4 - Mycotoxins in Animal Feed and Effects on Animal Production

Mycotoxins in animal feed pose a persistent global challenge, affecting animal health, production efficiency, and overall food chain safety. As a new use case introduced during the EFRA project, this activity, supported by Food Fortress Network members, aimed to explore how AI-driven analytics can enhance early detection, trend forecasting, and risk assessment for mycotoxin contamination in poultry and other livestock feed. Mycotoxins, produced by filamentous fungi, are known to impair nutrient utilisation, weaken immune function, and increase susceptibility to pathogens such as *Salmonella* spp., making proactive monitoring essential.

A key foundation of this work was the collaboration with Food Fortress, an internationally recognised feed quality assurance scheme in Northern Ireland. Food Fortress operates a large-scale, industry-wide risk management and testing programme, covering nearly 5 million tonnes of compound feed annually and involving more than 80 companies. Its decade-long dataset of detailed mycotoxin laboratory analyses provided a unique basis for developing the Mycotoxins Trend Prediction Model for Poultry Feed, enabling EFRA to analyse long-term patterns and understand how contamination evolves over time.

Building on this foundation, the use case explored how anonymised private datasets, laboratory test results, incident reports, trade flows, and weather indicators can be combined to forecast mycotoxin risks using public and private data sources. This approach supports a privacy-preserving scenario where insights are shared without exposing sensitive datasets, enabling more informed decision-making for feed manufacturers, poultry producers, and food safety authorities.

Use case Update

As the project progressed, the mycotoxins use case evolved from exploratory data analysis into two fully operational dashboards within the FOODAKAI platform, enabling both laboratory-driven monitoring and global incident-based forecasting for poultry and other animal feed.

(a) Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard

This dashboard has progressed from initial mock-ups to a production-ready module that visualises daily laboratory testing results for four key mycotoxins (Aflatoxin B1, Ochratoxin A, Zearalenone, and DON) across poultry and ram feed. Users can explore concentration trends over time, perform decomposition analysis, and inspect precise daily values through hover-based interaction. The dashboard provides a transparent

environment for identifying anomalies, seasonal patterns, and emerging risks, supporting both operational decision-making and laboratory quality assurance.

(b) Mycotoxins Incidents Forecasting Dashboard

Developed in parallel, this dashboard consolidates official mycotoxin-related incident announcements from major regulatory authorities, including RASFF and the U.S. FDA. It enables users to track historical incident patterns, forecast future trends, and detect emerging hazards in poultry and other animal feed. By integrating global incident data with EFRA's Timeseries Engine, the dashboard strengthens the ability of feed manufacturers, quality teams, and regulators to anticipate risks and prioritise preventive interventions.

3. EFRA'-S KPIs and Exploitation Plans

The present document represents the final version of the Integrated Toolset for Multiplying Impact and consolidates the framework established over the course of the EFRA project. Building on the previous versions (D6.2.1 and D6.2.2), which set out the foundational rules, principles, and recommendations for the protection and exploitation of project results, D6.2.3 reflects the full maturity of the EFRA outcomes and their readiness for uptake beyond the project duration.

In its final form, the toolset incorporates comprehensive updates to all previously identified KERs and formally includes the additional KERs developed during the later stages of the project. It provides a coherent and validated reference framework to support the sustainable exploitation, commercialisation, and reuse of EFRA services and tools, ensuring alignment with Horizon Europe requirements and long-term impact objectives.

3.1. Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

EFRA initially identified three key exploitable results (KERs) that are available for use/reuse by partners and target groups stakeholders. However, during the last reporting period five more KERs have been identified and added to the KERs Inventory & IPR tool for partners to examine, bringing the total number to eight.

1. **EFRA Analytics Powerhouse** – *(initial KER)*
2. **EFRA Data & Analytics Marketplace** – *(initial KER)*
3. **EFRA Data Hub** – *(initial KER)*
4. **RoBERTa-based web page classifier** (part of Data Hub) – *(added in D6.2.2)*
5. **Mycotoxins tailor-made AI predictive model & dashboards** (part of Analytics Powerhouse) – *(added in D6.2.2)*
6. **Mycotoxins occurrence data aggregation and harmonisation** (part of EFRA Data Hub) – *(added in D6.2.2)*
7. **Predictions Library** (part of the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse) – *(added in D6.2.2)*
8. **Extreme event forecasting** (part of EFRA Analytics Powerhouse) – *(added in D6.2.2)*
9. **Intelligent crawler for food-safety incident discovery** (part of EFRA Data Hub) – *(added in D6.2.3)*

From an exploitation perspective, all EFRA results have been assessed as suitable for both non-commercial and commercial exploitation pathways. They may be leveraged as technological building blocks, scientific knowledge assets, and validated prototypes, thereby supporting continued research and innovation in the fields of artificial intelligence and food risk prediction. At the same time, these results enable the development of new and market-ready services, tools, and processes. They could also contribute to the definition of future standards, best practices, and policy recommendations in the food safety domain.

Within this framework, the EFRA project has identified and documented its KERs, each accompanied by a clearly articulated Unique Value Proposition (UVP). The UVPs are designed as concise and accessible statements addressing both technical and non-technical stakeholders, explicitly describing the problem addressed by each KER and the specific value it delivers. The portfolio of KERs and corresponding UVPs has been continuously reviewed, updated, and validated through iterative development cycles aligned with the progress and timelines of the EFRA use cases, ensuring consistency, relevance, and readiness for exploitation at project completion.

Table 1: EFRA's Key Exploitable Results - Updated. (Marketability: C: Commercial, N: Non-commercial)

Exploitation Goal		By whom	For whom
KER 1 N&C	EFRA Analytics Powerhouse: Operational platform that runs over a dynamically managed green cloud HPC. It integrates a suite of advanced AI algorithms, multilingual NLU micro-modules, and data analytics components designed to support high-accuracy, explainable, and trustworthy food-risk prediction.		
<u>Academic & Research organisations:</u> Exploitation of scientific breakthroughs under other existing research activities in relevant domains, new research projects or for educational and training purposes. <u>Data scientists & analysts:</u> Reuse and enhance the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse solutions to build new tools/services, foster technological autonomy in data sharing and create thriving data economies.		AGROKNOW, CNR, SU, MAIZE	Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts
UVP	The EFRA Analytics Powerhouse delivers a cloud-native, energy-efficient environment that brings together advanced decision-making tools, multilingual natural-language-understanding micro-modules, and trustworthy, accurate, fair, and explainable AI models. By combining high-performance analytics with low energy consumption and seamless integration into the broader EFRA Platform, it enables food supply chain stakeholders to predict future food risks with confidence, reduce operational uncertainty, and accelerate the adoption of AI-driven preventive strategies across diverse contexts.		
KER 2 N&C	EFRA Data & Analytics Marketplace: A user-friendly web application that enables the discovery and access/use of raw data and pre-trained analytics services, available either for download or for direct execution on the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse. The Marketplace also provides access to third-party applications, through which the EFRA prediction AI models can be executed for the visualisation of model results.		
<u>Data owners</u> will use friendly services of the marketplace to publish information available on their own platforms (i.e., data providers) and monetize them. <u>Data consumers</u> (e.g., Food Safety Experts, Food System Stakeholders, Policy makers & regulators) will be able to explore available tools and information empowering their decision support processes.		AGROKNOW	Academic & Research organisations, Policy makers, Data scientists and data analysts, Food System Stakeholders and Safety Experts
UVP	Using a RESTful approach, the Marketplace allows new APIs and services to be added seamlessly, while keeping their implementation decoupled from the high-level functionality they provide. This ensures flexibility and smooth integration of data assets, pre-trained analytics services, and third-party applications within the EFRA Platform.		
KER 3 N&C	EFRA Data Hub: A data platform that crawls, aggregates, semantically enriches, aligns, and translates food-risk data from heterogeneous, multilingual public sources, as well as anonymised corporate datasets. It incorporates an Intelligent AI-driven crawler that automates the timely discovery and extraction of global food-safety incident data.		
<u>Academia:</u> Exploitation of the food safety risks data and the applied scientific underpinnings (e.g., pioneer NLP/NLU methods) for conducting new breakthrough research.		AGROKNOW, WFSR, MAIZE	Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts

	<u>Data scientists and data analysts</u> : Build new applications and services, utilising the hub to provide better, localised, and personalised services.		
UVP	The Data Hub is enriched with anonymised corporate datasets, and supply-chain data streams, including lab-testing results, IoT data, and relevant social-media content. This combination of public and private signals strengthens the coverage, granularity, and analytical value of the food-risk information powering the EFRA Platform.		
KER 4 N&C	RoBERTa-based web page classifier (part of Data Hub) : A RoBERTa-based classifier that identifies whether web pages are food-related and further categorises them as containing food-safety incidents or news. It supports the automated filtering of large volumes of online content, improving the precision and efficiency of the Data Hub's ingestion pipeline.		
	<u>Academia</u> : Exploitation of the food safety risks data and the applied scientific underpinnings (e.g., pioneer NLP/NLU methods) for conducting new breakthrough research. <u>Data scientists and data analysts</u> : Build new applications and services, utilising the hub to provide better, localised, and personalised services.	AGROKNOW	Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts
UVP	A RoBERTa-based classifier that identifies whether web pages are food-related and further categorises them as containing food-safety incidents or as news. It supports the automated filtering of large volumes of online content, improving the precision and efficiency of the Data Hub's ingestion pipeline.		
KER 5 N&C	Mycotoxins tailor-made AI predictive model & dashboards (part of Analytics Powerhouse) : The tailor-made AI predictive model and set of intuitive dashboards that provide customised mycotoxin-risk predictions for batches based on country of origin, target mycotoxin, and ingredient. The model combines public lab-testing data with weather and climate information to deliver precise, batch-specific risk assessments, fully integrated into the Analytics Powerhouse.		
	<u>Academia</u> : Exploitation of the food safety risks data and the applied scientific underpinnings (e.g., pioneer NLP/NLU methods) for conducting new breakthrough research. <u>Data scientists and data analysts</u> : Build new applications and services, utilising the hub to provide better, localised, and personalised services.	AGROKNOW	Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts
UVP	A tailor-made AI predictive model with intuitive dashboards that combine public lab tests with weather and climate data to deliver precise, batch-specific mycotoxin-risk assessments. It empowers decision-making with actionable insights to safeguard quality and compliance, seamlessly integrated into the Analytics Powerhouse.		
KER 6 N&C	Mycotoxins occurrence data aggregation and harmonisation (part of EFRA Data Hub) : Calibration and customization of Agroknow's data platform to collect, process and harmonize mycotoxins occurrence data in food and feed.		
	<u>Academia</u> : Exploitation of the food safety risks data and the applied scientific underpinnings (e.g., pioneer NLP/NLU methods) for conducting new breakthrough research.	AGROKNOW	Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts

<p><u>Data scientists and data analysts</u>: Build new applications and services, utilising the hub to provide better, localised, and personalised services.</p>		
<p>UVP</p>	<p>Unlock the power of harmonized mycotoxin data with advanced aggregation and calibration solutions. Tailored for the EFRA Data Hub, collect, process, and standardize mycotoxin occurrence data in food and feed, enabling seamless integration, improved data accuracy, and actionable insights for informed decision-making and compliance.</p>	
<p>KER 7 N&C</p>	<p>Predictions Library (part of the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse): Automates the selection of the best-performing time-series forecasting algorithm for each specific case, based on identified series characteristics. It provides a collection of pre-trained AI models that are accessible through the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse and can be directly used by upstream applications.</p>	
<p><u>Academia</u>: Exploitation of the food safety risks data and the applied scientific underpinnings (e.g., pioneer NLP/NLU methods) for conducting new breakthrough research.</p> <p><u>Data scientists and data analysts</u>: Build new applications and services, utilising the hub to provide better, localised, and personalised services.</p>	<p>AGROKNOW</p>	<p>Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts</p>
<p>UVP</p>	<p>Streamline forecasting with the Predictions Library, an automated component integrated into the Agroknow Data Platform that selects the optimal time-series algorithm for the selected data. Accessible through the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, it offers pre-trained trend-forecasting models for Salmonella risk in poultry and mycotoxin risks in animal feed/poultry, enabling upstream applications to generate precise, efficient, and actionable predictions.</p>	
<p>KER 8 N&C</p>	<p>Extreme event forecasting (part of EFRA Analytics Powerhouse): An AI model that estimates the likelihood that a time-series will surpass a predefined value threshold in the next time step. Integrated into the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, it supports proactive monitoring and early detection of emerging risks across dynamic datasets.</p>	
<p><u>Academia</u>: Exploitation of the food safety risks data and the applied scientific underpinnings (e.g., pioneer NLP/NLU methods) for conducting new breakthrough research.</p> <p><u>Data scientists and data analysts</u>: Build new applications and services, utilising the hub to provide better, localised, and personalised services.</p>	<p>AGROKNOW</p>	<p>Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts</p>
<p>UVP</p>	<p>Integrated into the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, this component delivers precise probability assessments for time-series exceeding predefined thresholds, enabling proactive decision-making and effective risk mitigation in dynamic environments.</p>	
<p>KER 9 N&C</p>	<p>Intelligent Crawler for Food-Safety Incident Discovery: An Intelligent AI agent crawler automates the discovery, validation, and extraction of food-safety incident data from global public sources. Built on a dual-model Generative AI architecture, it replaces manual web-scraping with an autonomous, multi-step pipeline. It is already implemented and tested within the Agroknow Data Platform. It enhances the scalability, coverage, and timeliness of data ingestion across multiple regions.</p>	
<p><u>Academia</u>: Access enriched, continuously updated food-safety incident datasets and the underlying AI</p>		<p>Academic & Research organisations, Data</p>

<p>methods to support new research and analytical innovation.</p> <p><u>Data scientists and data analysts</u>: Build new applications and services using scalable, continuously updated incident data, enabling more accurate, localised, and operationally robust analytics.</p>	<p>AGROKNOW</p>	<p>scientists and data analysts</p>
<p>UVP</p>	<p>An intelligent AI crawler that streamlines global food-safety incident acquisition through intelligent source discovery, validation, and extraction. Fully integrated into the Agroknow Data Platform, it delivers faster, broader, and more reliable incident coverage to support scalable monitoring and data-driven decision-making.</p>	

An exploitation strategy for the EFRA project was defined at an early stage of implementation (M3) within the framework of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) plan, and updates in M24. Its objective is to maximise the reach, uptake, and sustainability of project results beyond the project lifetime. This early and structured approach ensured that exploitation considerations were embedded throughout the project’s activities and decision-making processes.

The strategy follows a multi-actor, iterative approach structured around three complementary phases. The **Investigate phase** focused on the systematic identification of partner expectations and Intellectual Property (IP) requirements through IPR scans, bilateral consultations, and structured interviews, leading to the definition of tailored exploitation measures. The **Co-create phase** supported the continuous alignment of project results with evolving market trends, the validation of exploitation pathways, and the assessment of market fit for EFRA outcomes. Finally, the **Accelerate phase** culminated in the consolidation of exploitation agreements through dedicated workshops, the identification of cross-partner synergies, and the delivery of the Final Exploitation Plan. In parallel, a post-project sustainability framework has been established to safeguard the long-term viability and impact of EFRA results after the conclusion of the project.

3.2. Exploitation Plan

3.2.1. Exploitation methodology

A dedicated and structured procedure was defined and consistently applied throughout the EFRA project for the identification, validation, and management of KERs. This procedure covered the confirmation of initially identified KERs, the systematic identification of additional KERs emerging during the project, their validation and characterisation, and the development of tailored exploitation plans. Exploitation pathways were defined at the level of individual partners, groups of partners, or, where relevant, external organisations, ensuring clarity of roles and responsibilities and alignment with ownership and IPR arrangements.

The methodological framework supporting this process, including the registration of newly identified KERs in the EFRA “KERs Inventory & IPRs” online tool (Figure 1) and the step-by-step workflow for consortium-wide validation (Figure 2), was established earlier in the project and remains applicable in its final phase. A detailed description of this methodology is provided in the first iteration of this deliverable (D6.2.1), which serves as the reference document for the operational aspects of KER identification and validation.

KERs (Key Exploitable Results)	Scope of exploitation		Target groups [to whom]	Means of exploitation
<i>Please validate the already identified KERs (1-3) and add any other exploitable results if relevant</i>	<i>Please validate (for further explanation of the scope, please see note)</i>		<i>Please validate</i>	<i>Please indicate the means of exploitation, where relevant</i>
	<i>If "other", please identify</i>	<i>Other</i>		
1 EFRA Analytics Powerhouse	Commercial		Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts	<i>"This was initially identified as an exploitable result for your organisation. Could you please clarify how you envision its exploitation."</i>
2 EFRA Data and Analytics Marketplace: A web application that enables secure and user-friendly trading of datasets and AI models as assets, incorporating encryption and authentication measures	Commercial		Academic & Research organisations, Policy makers, Data scientists and data analysts, Food System Stakeholders and Safety Experts	<i>Creation of a new Trademark and integration inside the Agroknow ecosystem of solutions</i>
3 EFRA Data Hub	Commercial		Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts	<i>This was initially identified as an exploitable result for your organisation. Could you please clarify how you envision its exploitation.</i>

Figure 1: "KERs Inventory & IPRs" online tool

INCLUSION OF NEWLY IDENTIFIED KERs

Figure 2: Mapping of possible KERs procedure.

As part of the EFRA exploitation strategy, the BFMULO matrix has been employed as a central tool to support the systematic management of partner contributions and exploitation intentions. The matrix enables the registration of partners’ exploitation claims and expectations, providing a clear and structured overview of their intended involvement in each Key Exploitable Result (KER). Each letter within the BFMULO matrix corresponds to a specific type of exploitation intention, allowing for efficient mapping and coordination of roles across the consortium (see Table 2). This approach ensures transparency, facilitates strategic planning, and strengthens alignment between project outputs and partner exploitation objectives.

B = IPR’s on background information, information, excluding foreground information, brought to the project from existing knowledge, owned or controlled by project partners in the same or related fields of the work carried out in the research project.

F = IPR’s on foreground information, Information including all kinds of exploitable results generated by the project partners or 3rd parties working for them in the implementation of the research project. To have an F in an exploitable result it is necessary that a partner has a task(s) in the project related to that very result.

M = Making the products, manufacturing, and selling or directly implementing it through own facilities and skills.

U = Using the result, implemented with own knowledge to develop new ranges of products or newer processing. Furthermore, the direct or indirect utilisation of foreground in further research activities other than those covered by the project, or for developing, creating, and marketing a product or process, or for creating and providing a service.

L = Licensing the result, therefore earning from a negotiation towards third parties outside the Consortium.

O = Other, any other exploitation means (e.g.: consultancy, provide services, etc).

The table below (Table 2) presents the application of the BFMULO matrix to the eight (9) KERs, reflecting the respective exploitation intentions of the consortium partners. This initial mapping is based on discussions and agreements reached during the plenary meeting held in Athens and represents the first comprehensive attempt to populate the matrix for all KERs. This is the definitive version of the BFMULO matrix, incorporating final validations and any subsequent updates.

Table 2: EFRA's KERs BFMULO Matrix

	KER 1	KER 2	KER 3	KER 4	KER 5	KER 6	KER7	KER8	KER9
AGROKNOW	B,F,M,O	B,F,M, O	B,F,M,O						
CNR	B,F,O								
SU	B,F,O								
WR			B,F,O						
JAKALA	B,F,M,O		B,F,M,O						
AGRIVI									
RAIN	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SGS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
MOY	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

As a concluding step, a comprehensive characterisation table (Table 3) has been provided to partners responsible for exploiting the project's KERs. This table has been developed in this final deliverable, as the project results have matured and their added value within the EFRA platform has been fully validated. Each KER has been assigned a tailored exploitation approach, considering its specific type, potential for commercialisation, associated IPR requirements, and the responsible partner(s) for its exploitation. This ensures that all results are strategically positioned for effective uptake and sustainable impact.

Table 3: Characterization table for KERs

Characterization of Exploitable Results	
Market	Who will the customer be and what benefits will they receive?
	What is the anticipated time for the market launch?
	What is the size of the market in M€ and the relevant trends?
	What is the approximate price range of this result and price of relevant licences?
	Who are the competitors?
	How will this result rank against competing products/services in terms of price and/or performance?
Steps towards exploitation	When is the expected date of achievement?
	What are the foreseen barriers to successful implementation?
	What are the costs incurred (if any) after the project and before exploitation?
	Which partners will be involved in results development?
IPR status	Have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When?

Table 4: Characterization table for KER#1 EFRA Analytics Powerhouse

Characterization of KER#1: EFRA Analytics Powerhouse	
Market	<p>Who will the customer/user be and what benefits will they receive?</p> <p><u>Primary customers</u>: Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists & analysts, Food-system stakeholders, Food-safety authorities, Industry risk-management teams.</p> <p><u>Benefits</u>: Access to a cloud-native, energy-efficient environment offering advanced AI models, multilingual NLU micro-modules, and high-performance analytics for food-risk prediction. Enables faster, more accurate, explainable, and trustworthy decision-making.</p>
	<p>What is the anticipated time for the market launch?</p> <p>Already operational within the EFRA Platform from M24 of the project lifetime for executing the EFRA prediction AI models.</p>
	<p>What is the size of the market in M€ and the relevant trends?</p> <p>It is not positioned as a standalone product but as a core component within broader food-safety and analytics infrastructures. It can be integrated into the global food-safety testing and analytics market, estimated at around 20B Euros, driven by increasing regulatory requirements, supply-chain complexity, and the growing adoption of predictive analytics and AI-enabled early-warning systems.</p>
	<p>What is the approximate price range of this result and price of relevant licences?</p> <p>N/A (not offered as a standalone commercial product)</p>
	<p>Who are the competitors?</p> <p><u>Domain-specific food-risk intelligence platforms</u>: Agroknow Data Platform, SGS Digicomply, FoodChain ID, IBM Food Trust</p> <p><u>Generic AI/ML platforms</u>: AWS, Azure, Google Cloud. No major platform currently offers standalone food-safety AI models for direct execution.</p>
	<p>How will this result rank against competing products/services in terms of price and/or performance?</p> <p><u>Price</u>: N/A, as it is not offered as a standalone commercial product.</p> <p><u>Performance</u>: Higher accuracy, explainability, and domain-specificity through specialised AI models and multilingual NLU. More efficient execution than local infrastructure, with faster computational times enabled by optimised cloud-based pipelines.</p> <p><u>Differentiator</u>: Combines trustworthy AI, multilingual capabilities, and food-risk-specific models not available in generic platforms, while also enabling the integration and further development of academic research models—extending capabilities beyond what commercial platforms typically provide.</p>
Steps towards exploitation	<p>When is the expected date of achievement?</p> <p>Already achieved by M24</p>

	<p>What are the foreseen barriers to successful implementation?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manual configuration and API validation required for external users to execute models directly through the Powerhouse. - Integration of additional AI models requiring ongoing maintenance, testing, and alignment with the platform’s execution framework. - Continuous model upkeep, ensuring models remain updated with the latest validated versions beyond the project’s lifetime.
	<p>What are the costs incurred (if any) after the project and before exploitation?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cloud infrastructure and HPC execution costs, estimated at 15.000 Euros annually, depending on usage (model runs, storage, data transfer). - AI model maintenance and updates, carried out periodically by research partners as part of their regular research activity, while commercial models are updated within the companies’ normal business processes. - Platform maintenance and support, including integration of new models and technical upkeep, estimated at 15.000 Euros annually (approx. 1 person for 2 days/month from the Jakala team).
	<p>Which partners will be involved in results development?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Jakala, responsible for platform development, integration, and ongoing maintenance. - AGROKNOW, CNR, and SU, responsible for scientific validation, development, and maintenance of the EFRA Platform components.
IPR status	<p>Have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The EFRA Analytics Powerhouse (Jakala) is protected through copyright, proprietary software licensing, and restricted access to model weights, APIs, and execution pipelines. - EFRA Platform components provided by AGROKNOW, SU, CNR, and Jakala may additionally be protected through trade secrets covering algorithms, data-processing workflows, and optimisation techniques.

Table 5: Characterization table for KER#2 EFRA Data & Analytics Marketplace

Characterization of KER#2: EFRA Data & Analytics Marketplace	
Market	<p>Who will the customer/user be and what benefits will they receive?</p> <p><u>Primary customers:</u> Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists & analysts, Food-system stakeholders, Food-safety authorities, Industry risk-management teams.</p> <p><u>Benefits:</u> A user-friendly web application enabling discovery, access, and use of raw datasets, pre-trained analytics services, and third-party applications. It supports continuous updates of the EFRA datasets through API-based synchronisation and provides a unified entry point for both data owners and data consumers.</p>

	<p>What is the anticipated time for the market launch?</p> <p>Already accessible from M34 of the project lifetime.</p>
	<p>What is the size of the market in M€ and the relevant trends?</p> <p>The Marketplace aligns with the broader food-data and analytics ecosystem, a multi-billion Euros market driven by regulatory transparency, interoperability needs, and the adoption of AI-enabled decision-support tools.</p>
	<p>What is the approximate price range of this result and price of relevant licences?</p> <p>The pricing and access model consists of three layers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EFRA datasets and AI models are accessible free of charge, as they have been developed within the EFRA project. - Third-party datasets, Data APIs, and software applications require user registration but no additional subscription or connection cost within the Marketplace. Licensing payments for third-party assets (datasets, data APIs, or software applications) are handled directly between the user and the external provider, since the user is redirected from the Marketplace to the provider’s subscription page. The Marketplace receives a referral fee, typically: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 10% for third-party software applications · 15% for data APIs · E.g. for a 10.000 Euros annual subscription to a third-party system, the Marketplace would receive 1.000 Euros (10%) as a referral fee. - Data-Sharing Network service: The creation of private data-sharing networks for exchanging anonymised datasets is available to registered users. Participation for each network member is offered under a subscription-based model starting at 5.000 Euros per member annually, covering setup and maintenance costs.

Who are the competitors?

- Direct Competitors - Food & Agriculture Domain Platforms: Platforms offering datasets, analytics modules, APIs, or multi-component software relevant to food safety, compliance, and risk intelligence:

- Agroknow's FOODAKAI: Multi-module food-risk intelligence platform with dashboards, analytics, and data access, combined with RISKDATA, the food-risk intelligence APIs providing structured data feeds (<https://www.foodakai.com>)
- FoodChain ID: Regulatory intelligence, compliance workflows, ingredient risk (<https://www.foodchainid.com>)
- SGS Digicomply: Regulatory monitoring, datasets, risk insights (<https://www.digicomply.com>)
- Safefood.ai: AI-driven food-risk monitoring and early-warning signals (<https://safefood.ai>)
- IBM Food Trust: Blockchain-based traceability and supply-chain transparency (<https://www.ibm.com/support/pages/ibm-food-trust-building-apps-overview>)
- TraceGains: Supplier compliance, documentation, ingredient intelligence (<https://www.tracegains.com>)
- FoodLogiQ: Traceability, incident management, supplier data (<https://www.foodlogiq.com>)

- Adjacent Platforms (Compliance, ESG, Supply-Chain Risk) - Platforms that combine datasets, APIs, analytics, and software modules and could expand into food-risk analytics:

- Dun & Bradstreet (D&B): Supply-chain risk scoring, data APIs (<https://www.dnb.com>)
- EcoVadis: ESG ratings, supplier performance analytics (<https://ecovadis.com>)
- Intertek InSight: Compliance data, dashboards, supply-chain monitoring (<https://www.intertek.com/assurance/insight>)
- SAP Business Network: Supply-chain data, analytics, partner applications (<https://www.sap.com/products/business-network.html>)

- Generic Data & AI Marketplaces (Datasets + APIs + AI Models + Software Tools) - These platforms offer datasets, data APIs, pre-trained AI models, and multiple software applications. While not food-specific, their scale and technical flexibility give them the ability to adapt to the food-risk domain, making them potential competitors:

- AWS Data Exchange: Datasets, APIs, ML models, analytics tools (<https://aws.amazon.com/data-exchange/>)
- Microsoft Azure Marketplace: Data services, AI models, APIs, deployable applications (<https://azuremarketplace.microsoft.com/>)
- Google Cloud Marketplace: Datasets, ML APIs, third-party applications (<https://console.cloud.google.com/marketplace>)
- Databricks Marketplace: Datasets, ML models, notebooks, partner apps (<https://marketplace.databricks.com/>)
- Hugging Face Hub: Datasets, pre-trained AI models, inference APIs, integrations (<https://huggingface.co/>)

	<p>How will this result rank against competing products/services in terms of price and/or performance?</p> <p><u>Price:</u> EFRA is more cost-effective than competing platforms because EFRA datasets and AI models are free to access, with costs only arising for optional third-party services.</p> <p><u>Performance:</u> EFRA outperforms competitors by combining domain-specific datasets, specialised food-risk AI models, and integrated execution pipelines in a single environment.</p>
<p>Steps towards exploitation</p>	<p>When is the expected date of achievement?</p> <p>Already achieved by M34</p>
	<p>What are the foreseen barriers to successful implementation?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintaining continuous synchronisation of EFRA datasets and analytics services as partners update their assets. - Encouraging data owners to publish and maintain high quality metadata and documentation. - Further promotion activities directly to the data / predictive AI models providers (Research) and potential adopters (Industry, Research)
	<p>What are the costs incurred (if any) after the project and before exploitation?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintaining continuous synchronisation of EFRA datasets and analytics services, as partners update their assets, estimated at 15.000 Euros annually (approx. 1 person for 1 day/month from the Agroknow team, plus hosting services). - Sustained engagement with data owners, particularly researchers, to encourage publication, documentation, and sharing of research datasets with sufficient metadata quality. - Outreach and promotion activities targeting data providers, predictive-model developers, and potential adopters across industry and research, ensuring continued growth of the EFRA ecosystem.
	<p>Which partners will be involved in results development?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AGROKNOW, responsible for platform development, integration, and ongoing maintenance. - All EFRA partners, as EFRA assets providers
<p>IPR status</p>	<p>Have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The EFRA Data & Analytics Marketplace (AGROKNOW) is protected through copyright, proprietary software licensing, and restricted access to model weights, APIs, and execution pipelines. - EFRA assets (datasets, predictive AI models, decision-support tools) provided by partners may also be protected through trade secrets covering algorithms, data-processing workflows, and optimisation techniques.

Table 6: Characterization table for KER#3 EFRA Data Hub

Characterization of KER#3: EFRA Data Hub	
Market	<p>Who will the customer be and what benefits will they receive?</p> <p><u>Primary customers:</u> Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts, Food-system stakeholders, Food-safety authorities, Industry risk-management teams.</p> <p><u>Benefits:</u> The EFRA Data Hub provides intelligent crawlers and data annotation & linking modules that search, mine, process, annotate, and link dispersed, multilingual, heterogeneous, and deep/hidden food-safety data sources. It aggregates public food-risk data with anonymised corporate datasets, enabling richer, more granular, and more actionable food-risk intelligence for research, analytics, and application development.</p>
	<p>What is the anticipated time for the market launch?</p> <p>Already accessible from M24 of the project lifetime.</p>
	<p>What is the size of the market in M€ and the relevant trends?</p> <p>The EFRA Data Hub operates within the food-risk intelligence and food-safety data market, valued at 2.7-3.8B Euros, growing at about 8% per year due to rising food-safety incidents, stricter regulations, and increasing demand for real-time, multilingual, AI-driven monitoring.</p>
	<p>What is the approximate price range of this result and price of relevant licences?</p> <p>The EFRA Data Hub is provided as a core EFRA component and is accessible to EFRA partners and Marketplace users without additional licensing fees. Additional effort arises only for optional services, such as third-party datasets integrated through the EFRA Marketplace when users choose to subscribe to those external providers.</p>
	<p>Who are the competitors?</p> <p>Platforms offering food-safety datasets and data-annotation services include SGS Digicomply, Safefood.ai, FoodChain ID, and Agroknow’s FOODAKAI/RISKDATA, which provide structured datasets, incident monitoring, and multilingual extraction. Public dataset providers such as EFSA OpenFoodTox, FDA, and FSA/FSS also overlap with EFRA’s data-collection scope. Adjacent competitors include Expert.ai, Ontotext, and Databricks Marketplace, which offer NLP, semantic enrichment, and data-integration services applicable to food-safety data.</p>
	<p>How will this result rank against competing products/services in terms of price and/or performance?</p> <p><u>Price:</u> The EFRA Data Hub is more cost-effective than competing platforms, as its core data-integration services are provided without additional licensing fees.</p> <p><u>Performance:</u> It outperforms competitors by combining intelligent crawling, semantic enrichment, multilingual alignment, and integration of anonymised corporate datasets in a single, domain-tailored environment.</p>

Steps towards exploitation	<p>When is the expected date of achievement?</p> <p>Already achieved by M24</p>
	<p>What are the foreseen barriers to successful implementation?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manual configuration, validation, and continuous tuning of the intelligent crawlers to ensure reliable extraction from heterogeneous, multilingual food-safety data sources. - Integration of additional public and corporate datasets requiring ongoing maintenance, semantic alignment, and quality-assurance workflows within the Data Hub. - Sustained upkeep of the data-processing pipelines (crawling, enrichment, annotation, linking) to ensure they remain accurate, up-to-date, and compatible with evolving data formats and regulatory sources.
	<p>What are the costs incurred (if any) after the project and before exploitation?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cloud infrastructure and data-processing costs, estimated at 15,000 Euros annually, depending on crawler activity, storage volume, and frequency of multilingual data ingestion. - Maintenance and updates of the intelligent crawlers, including periodic adjustments to source structures, language models, and extraction rules, carried out by AGROKNOW and research partners as part of their ongoing activities. - Platform maintenance and support, including semantic-enrichment pipeline upkeep, integration of new data sources, and technical monitoring, estimated at 15,000 Euros annually (approx. 1 person for 2 days/month).
	<p>Which partners will be involved in results development?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Jakala, responsible for platform development, integration, and ongoing maintenance. - AGROKNOW, Moy Park, WFSR, SGS and Agrivi, responsible for scientific validation, development, and maintenance of the EFRA Platform components.
IPR status	<p>Have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The EFRA Data Hub (Jakala) is protected through copyright, proprietary software licensing, and restricted access to model weights, APIs, and execution pipelines. - EFRA Platform components provided by AGROKNOW, SU, and Jakala may additionally be protected through trade secrets covering algorithms, data-processing workflows, and optimisation techniques.

Table 7: Characterization table for KER#4 RoBERTa-based web page classifier

Characterization of KER#4: RoBERTa-based web page classifier	
Market	<p>Who will the customer be and what benefits will they receive?</p> <p><u>Primary customers:</u> Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts, Food-system stakeholders, Food-safety authorities, and industry risk-management teams.</p> <p><u>Benefits:</u> The RoBERTa-based classifier automatically identifies whether web pages are food-related and further categorises them as food-safety incidents or general news. It enables high-precision filtering of large volumes of online content, significantly improving the efficiency, accuracy, and scalability of the EFRA Data Hub’s ingestion pipeline and supporting downstream analytics and research.</p>
	<p>What is the anticipated time for the market launch?</p> <p>Already available from M16 of the project lifetime.</p>
	<p>What is the size of the market in M€ and the relevant trends?</p> <p>N/A - The classifier contributes to the broader market for AI-driven text classification and automated content filtering</p>
	<p>What is the approximate price range of this result and price of relevant licences?</p> <p>N/A</p>
	<p>Who are the competitors?</p> <p>The EFRA classifier competes primarily with SGS Digicomply, Safefood.ai, FoodChain ID/Decernis, Neogen, TraceGains, and FOODAKAI, which provide automated extraction and categorisation of food-safety information.</p>
	<p>How will this result rank against competing products/services in terms of price and/or performance?</p> <p><u>Performance:</u> Outperforms generic NLP models by offering domain-specific classification tuned to food-safety incidents, multilingual content, and EFRA’s ingestion requirements.</p>
Steps towards exploitation	<p>When is the expected date of achievement?</p> <p>Already achieved by M16</p>
	<p>What are the foreseen barriers to successful implementation?</p> <p>- Continuous retraining and fine-tuning required to maintain high accuracy as new food-safety terminology, languages, and content patterns emerge.</p>
	<p>What are the costs incurred (if any) after the project and before exploitation?</p> <p>- Model maintenance and retraining, including periodic updates to training datasets and fine-tuning cycles, estimated at 7.000 annually (approx. 1 person for 1 day/ 6 months).</p>

	<p>Which partners will be involved in results development?</p> <p>AGROKNOW, responsible for model development, fine-tuning, integration, and ongoing maintenance within the Data Hub.</p>
IPR status	<p>Have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When?</p> <p>The RoBERTa-based classifier (AGROKNOW) is protected through copyright, proprietary software licensing, and restricted access to model weights, training datasets, and inference pipelines.</p>

Table 8: Characterization table for KER#5 *Mycotoxins tailor-made AI predictive model & dashboards*

Characterization of KER#5: Mycotoxins tailor-made AI predictive model & dashboards	
Market	<p>Who will the customer be and what benefits will they receive?</p> <p><u>Primary customers:</u> Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts, Food-system stakeholders, Food-safety authorities, Quality-assurance teams, and industry risk-management units.</p> <p><u>Benefits:</u> The tailor-made AI predictive model provides batch-specific mycotoxin-risk predictions based on country of origin, target mycotoxin, and ingredient (animal feed crop). By combining public lab-testing data with weather and climate information, it delivers precise, early, and actionable risk assessments. The accompanying dashboard offers intuitive visualisation that support decision-making, quality control, and compliance management.</p>
	<p>What is the anticipated time for the market launch?</p> <p>Already available from M30 of the project lifetime.</p>
	<p>What is the size of the market in M€ and the relevant trends?</p> <p>This result contributes to the animal-feed safety and quality-assurance market, a specialised segment within the broader food-safety analytics domain. This market is valued at 1,2-1,6B Euros.</p>
	<p>What is the approximate price range of this result and price of relevant licences?</p> <p>The predictive model is available through the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse and the Marketplace at no extra licensing cost. Full visualisation is provided via the EFRA Decision Support Tool in Agroknow’s FOODAKAI application. When included in a broader risk-intelligence service covering additional risks or ingredients, annual subscription typically starts at 30.000 Euros per year.</p>
	<p>Who are the competitors?</p> <p>Competitors include platforms that provide ingredient-risk monitoring, contamination alerts, and predictive or near-real-time risk-intelligence services, directly comparable to the capabilities delivered through FOODAKAI. These include HorizonScan, SGS Digicomply, Safefood.ai, FoodChain ID / Decernis, TraceGains, and Neogen’s risk-monitoring services, all of which offer structured datasets, alerts, or contamination-trend analytics for food and feed ingredients.</p>

	<p>How will this result rank against competing products/services in terms of price and/or performance?</p> <p><u>Performance:</u> It offers a unique combination of public lab-testing data, weather and climate indicators, and ingredient-specific modelling, providing a level of domain-tailored prediction that most competitors do not match. Full visualisation of the predictive-model results is already integrated into a commercial software application (FOODAKAI), ensuring high usability and seamless decision support.</p>
Steps towards exploitation	<p>When is the expected date of achievement?</p> <p>Already achieved by M30</p>
	<p>What are the foreseen barriers to successful implementation?</p> <p>To ensure continuous updates of public lab-testing and climate datasets and maintaining high predictive accuracy as contamination patterns evolve. Periodic model retraining and validation will be required to sustain performance over time.</p>
	<p>What are the costs incurred (if any) after the project and before exploitation?</p> <p>The predictive model operates within Agroknow's automated infrastructure, where maintenance, retraining, and monitoring are part of the regular process for all prediction models. No manual work is required. The only cost incurred before exploitation is a small cloud-hosting expense, typically below €1,000 per year.</p>
	<p>Which partners will be involved in results development?</p> <p>Agroknow will be responsible for maintaining and operating the AI prediction model within its automated infrastructure.</p>
IPR status	<p>Have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When?</p> <p>The predictive model and dashboards are protected through copyright, proprietary software licensing, and restricted access to model weights, training datasets, and inference pipelines.</p>

Table 9: Characterization table for KER#6 *Mycotoxins occurrence data aggregation and harmonisation*

Characterization of KER#6: Mycotoxins occurrence data aggregation and harmonisation	
Market	<p>Who will the customer be and what benefits will they receive?</p> <p><u>Primary customers:</u> Academic and research organisations, data scientists and data analysts, and industry users who rely on accurate contaminant-occurrence information for research, modelling, and operational decision-making.</p> <p><u>Benefits:</u> They gain access to harmonised, high-quality mycotoxin-occurrence datasets that improve data accuracy, support advanced research, and enable the development of new data-driven applications and services within the EFRA Data Hub.</p>
	<p>What is the anticipated time for the market launch?</p> <p>Already available from M20 of the project lifetime</p>
	<p>What is the size of the market in M€ and the relevant trends?</p> <p>This result contributes to the broader food-safety data and analytics market, valued at approximately 500–700M Euros, driven by increasing regulatory pressure, digitalisation of food-safety workflows, and the growing need for harmonised contaminant-occurrence datasets.</p>
	<p>What is the approximate price range of this result and price of relevant licences?</p> <p>N/A</p>
	<p>Who are the competitors?</p> <p>HorizonScan, SGS Digicomply, FOODAKAI, Safefood.ai, FoodChain ID, TraceGains</p>
	<p>How will this result rank against competing products/services in terms of price and/or performance?</p> <p>Performance is superior due to the automated aggregation, harmonisation, and calibration of public mycotoxin-occurrence data, offering a level of data quality, consistency, and interoperability that most competitors do not match.</p>
Steps towards exploitation	<p>When is the expected date of achievement?</p> <p>Already achieved by M20</p>
	<p>What are the foreseen barriers to successful implementation?</p> <p>The main barriers relate to ensuring continuous updates of public mycotoxin-occurrence datasets and maintaining high harmonisation accuracy as new data sources or formats emerge.</p>
	<p>What are the costs incurred (if any) after the project and before exploitation?</p> <p>The data-aggregation and harmonisation pipelines run as a semi-automatic process within Agroknow's infrastructure. This is part of normal operations, with cloud-hosting and limited personnel time amounting to less than 8.000 Euros annually.</p>

Which partners will be involved in results development?	Which partners will be involved in results development? Agroknow will maintain and operate the automated data-aggregation and harmonisation pipelines.
IPR status	Have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When? The aggregation workflows, harmonisation logic, and calibration methods are protected through copyright and kept as proprietary internal processes within Agroknow.

Table 10: Characterization table for KER#7 Predictions Library

Characterization of KER#7: Predictions Library	
Market	<p>Who will the customer be and what benefits will they receive?</p> <p><u>Primary customers</u>: Academic and research organisations, data scientists and data analysts, and industry users who rely on time-series forecasting for risk assessment, modelling, and operational decision-making.</p> <p><u>Benefits</u>: They gain access to continuously updated and re-trained pre-trained forecasting models that deliver efficient, accurate, and ready-to-use predictions through the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse.</p>
	<p>What is the anticipated time for the market launch?</p> <p>Already available from M15 of the project lifetime</p>
	<p>What is the size of the market in M€ and the relevant trends?</p> <p>This result contributes to the broader AI-driven forecasting and food-safety analytics market, valued at approximately 500–700M Euros, with strong growth driven by the adoption of automated modelling pipelines, demand for AI-ready data, and the integration of forecasting components into digital food-safety systems.</p>
	<p>What is the approximate price range of this result and price of relevant licences?</p> <p>This component is part of Agroknow’s backend process for creating and updating forecasting models for each ingredient and risk. The updated prediction AI models are accessible through the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, and full visualisation is already integrated into the relevant dashboards within the FOODAKAI application.</p>
	<p>Who are the competitors?</p> <p>HorizonScan, SGS Digicomply, Safefood.ai, FoodChain ID, and TraceGains</p>
	<p>How will this result rank against competing products/services in terms of price and/or performance?</p> <p>Performance is superior due to its automated model-selection mechanism, which identifies the optimal time-series algorithm based on dataset characteristics, and its continuously updated pre-trained models (e.g., for Salmonella risks). Most competitors do not offer automated forecasting pipelines or ingredient-specific pre-trained models.</p>

Steps towards exploitation	When is the expected date of achievement? Already achieved by M15
	What are the foreseen barriers to successful implementation? The main barrier is ensuring continuous updates and retraining of forecasting models as new data becomes available. Maintaining high predictive performance requires periodic validation and algorithmic refreshes.
	What are the costs incurred (if any) after the project and before exploitation? This component is part of Agroknow’s normal model-maintenance workflow. Model updates and algorithm selection are integrated into existing processes.
	Which partners will be involved in results development? Agroknow is responsible for maintaining and operating the AI prediction-model mechanisms.
IPR status	Have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When? The predictive AI models are protected through copyright, proprietary software licensing, and restricted access to model weights, training datasets, and inference pipelines.

Table 11: Characterization table for KER#8 Extreme event forecasting

Characterization of KER#8: Extreme event forecasting	
Market	Who will the customer be and what benefits will they receive? <u>Primary customers:</u> Academic and research organisations, data scientists and data analysts, and industry users who require early-warning signals for emerging risks in dynamic datasets. <u>Benefits:</u> They gain access to an AI model that estimates the probability of a time-series exceeding predefined thresholds, enabling proactive monitoring, early detection of anomalies, and timely risk-mitigation actions through the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse.
	What is the anticipated time for the market launch? Already available from M20 of the project lifetime
	What is the size of the market in M€ and the relevant trends? The market is valued at 500–700M Euros, driven by growing demand for predictive analytics, early-warning systems, and AI integration in food-safety and supply-chain monitoring.
	What is the approximate price range of this result and price of relevant licences? N/A

	<p>Who are the competitors?</p> <p>Competitors include analytics and food-safety intelligence providers such as HorizonScan, SGS Digicomply, Safefood.ai, FoodChain ID, and TraceGains.</p>
	<p>How will this result rank against competing products/services in terms of price and/or performance?</p> <p>Performance is superior due to its specialised AI model for predicting threshold-exceeding events and its integration into a unified analytics environment.</p>
Steps towards exploitation	<p>When is the expected date of achievement?</p> <p>Already achieved by M20</p>
	<p>What are the foreseen barriers to successful implementation?</p> <p>The main barrier is ensuring continuous validation and recalibration of the model as new data becomes available, to maintain high accuracy and minimise false alarms.</p>
	<p>What are the costs incurred (if any) after the project and before exploitation?</p> <p>This component is part of Agroknow’s normal model-maintenance workflow. Updates and recalibration are integrated into existing processes.</p>
	<p>Which partners will be involved in results development?</p> <p>Agroknow will be responsible for maintaining and operating the extreme-event forecasting mechanisms.</p>
IPR status	<p>Have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When?</p> <p>The extreme-event forecasting models are protected through copyright, proprietary software licensing, and restricted access to model weights, training datasets, and inference pipelines.</p>

Table 12: Characterization table for KER#9 Intelligent Crawler for Food-Safety Incident Discovery

Characterization of KER#9: Intelligent Crawler for Food-Safety Incident Discovery	
Market	<p>Who will the customer be and what benefits will they receive?</p> <p><u>Primary customers:</u> Academic and research organisations, data scientists and data analysts, and industry users who rely on timely, high-quality food-safety incident data.</p> <p><u>Benefits:</u> They gain access to enriched, validated, and continuously updated food-safety incident datasets generated through an autonomous AI-driven discovery and extraction pipeline, enabling more accurate, localised, and operationally robust analytics.</p>
	<p>What is the anticipated time for the market launch?</p> <p>Already available from M32 of the project lifetime</p>
	<p>What is the size of the market in M€ and the relevant trends?</p> <p>N/A</p>
	<p>What is the approximate price range of this result and price of relevant licences?</p> <p>N/A</p>
	<p>Who are the competitors?</p> <p>Competitors include specialised IT and data-extraction companies that provide automated web-crawling, AI-driven data-mining, or large-scale information-harvesting solutions, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diffbot - AI-powered automated web extraction and knowledge graph creation (https://www.diffbot.com) - Import.io - Enterprise-scale intelligent web data extraction (https://www.import.io) - Zyte (formerly Scrapinghub) - Intelligent crawling, structured extraction, and large-scale scraping pipelines (https://www.zyte.com) - Bright Data - Web-scraping infrastructure, proxy networks, and automated data-collection tools (https://brightdata.com)
	<p>How will this result rank against competing products/services in terms of price and/or performance?</p> <p>Performance is superior due to its autonomous, multi-step AI pipeline for source discovery, validation, and extraction, while most competitors rely on manual or semi-automated scraping. Further refinement (e.g. enhanced detail extraction and stronger production-grade integration) will continue to improve scalability and robustness.</p>
Steps towards exploitation	<p>When is the expected date of achievement?</p> <p>Already achieved by M32</p>

	<p>What are the foreseen barriers to successful implementation?</p> <p>The main barriers include adapting the crawler to evolving website structures, ensuring reliable extraction of full incident details, and maintaining robust error-handling and monitoring as the system scales.</p>
	<p>What are the costs incurred (if any) after the project and before exploitation?</p> <p>The main barriers include adapting the crawler to evolving website structures, reliably extracting full incident details, selecting and ranking the most appropriate sources for harvesting, and maintaining robust error-handling and monitoring as the system scales.</p>
	<p>Which partners will be involved in results development?</p> <p>Agroknow will be responsible for maintaining and further developing the intelligent crawler mechanisms.</p>
<p>IPR status</p>	<p>Have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When?</p> <p>Agroknow protects the intelligent crawler and its AI-driven extraction workflows through copyright, proprietary software licensing, and restricted access to model weights, training datasets, and inference pipelines.</p>

4. Market Analysis

An in-depth market assessment of the EFRA platform and its 4 use cases was included in the earlier iterations of this deliverable (D6.2.1 and D6.2.2). The present chapter complements the previous analysis with updated figures derived from recent market reports.

4.1. EFRA position in the Data Market

The analysis begins with an updated for 2024 overview of the European Data Market, where experts express strong confidence in its trajectory. Key metrics monitored by the European Data Monitoring Tool³ show sustained acceleration. Drawing from the most recent report, which extends coverage to 2024 (surpassing the earlier 2023 cutoff) the standout figures include:

- 5.2% year-over-year increase in Data Professionals
- 10.1% year-over-year increase in Data Suppliers
- 4.1% year-over-year increase in Data Users

These gains reflect a vibrant data economy, with market valuations delivering even more striking results that highlight adaptation to cutting-edge trends:

- 12.4% year-over-year rise in Data Market value (from USD 82 billion to USD 92 billion)
- 10.2% year-over-year rise in overall Data Economy value (from USD 544 billion to USD 599 billion)

For the horizon through 2030, EU forecasts present baseline and high-growth paths. The influential Draghi report⁴ has sparked fresh dialogue on Europe's data ambitions. Pre-dating this, the original estimates have evolved. D6.2.3 integrates revisions aligned with the new European Parliament and Commission's goals, resulting in the 2025-2030 outlook:

- 3.8% - 7.4% CAGR for Data Professionals
- 3.7% - 4.8% CAGR for Data Companies
- 3.6% - 7.5% CAGR for Data Market value

Data Market spending in 2024 claimed 12.8% of EU27 ICT budgets, advancing from 12.0% the year prior. Powerhouses like Germany, France, Italy, the Netherlands, and Spain drove over 69% of this activity, reinforcing how data prowess aligns with sophisticated, tech-forward economies.

Navigating inflation and geopolitical flux, a 2024 IDC poll indicated 72% of European firms intend to ramp up ICT spending in 2025⁵. Such momentum owes much to policy levers like Next Generation EU funds, funnelling substantial resources into digital transformation.

Artificial Intelligence stands as the powerhouse fuelling this surge, with projections signalling rapid expansion. Dimension Market Research⁶ anticipates the European Generative AI market will leap from USD 12.4 billion in 2025 to USD 89 billion by 2034, at a 24.5% CAGR, led by text applications over image and audio segments.

³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/european-data-market-study-2024-2026>

⁴ https://commission.europa.eu/topics/strengthening-european-competitiveness/eu-competitiveness-looking-ahead_en#paragraph_47059

⁵ <https://www.idc.com/getdoc.jsp?containerId=EUR247892624>

⁶ <https://dimensionmarketresearch.com/>

4.1.1. Market analysis of food safety risk/fraud prediction

Food testing stands as a critical safeguard for global health. The World Health Organization (WHO)⁷ estimates that tainted food triggers about 600 million illnesses each year worldwide, claiming 420,000 lives and erasing 33 million healthy life years (DALYs).

These incidents inflict profound damage on health systems and economies, with losses topping USD 110 billion annually in low- and middle-income nations. Children under five suffer disproportionately, comprising 40% of foodborne cases and accounting for 125,000 deaths yearly

Prioritizing food safety unlocks better public well-being and economic stability. The global food safety testing market reached USD 24.10B in 2025, with projections to climb to USD 42.37B by 2033 at a 7.31% CAGR⁸. In Europe specifically, this sector eyes USD 6.92B in 2025, expanding to USD 10.74B by 2033 via a 5.84% CAGR⁹.

The European Food Safety Authority upholds traceability standards under Regulation (EC) No. 178/2002¹⁰ mandating end-to-end tracking in food and beverage chains to counter supply risks.

Global food traceability efforts underscore this momentum, valued at USD 18.82B in 2025 per Coherent Market Insights¹¹. Alternative estimates peg it at USD 24.07B in 2025¹². Meanwhile the forecast is expected to hit USD 32.43B by 2032 (8.1% CAGR)¹¹, or USD 46.74B (9.88% CAGR)¹², propelled by regulations.

Food traceability software, as detailed by Verified Market Research¹³ hit USD 385M in 2025 (adjusted from 2024's USD 325.64M base), targeting USD 662.44M by 2031 at a 10.24% CAGR.

Consumer demand for secure food sources, alongside rising outbreaks, will intensify reliance on these tools, curbing health threats through 2032.

4.1.2. Risk Prediction in Food Safety

Risk prediction in food safety now increasingly depends on large-scale data analytics and AI models that integrate information from across the supply chain, covering production, processing, distribution, and retail environments^{14,15,16,17}. By combining historical incident records with real-time data streams (e.g. temperature and humidity logs, logistics and storage conditions, sensor readings, laboratory results, and supplier performance), machine learning and deep learning systems can anticipate contamination events, spoilage risks, and foodborne outbreaks earlier and with higher precision than traditional rule-based

⁷ <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/food-safety>

⁸ <https://straitresearch.com/report/food-safety-testing-market>

⁹ <https://www.coherentmarketinsights.com/industry-reports/food-traceability-market>

¹⁰ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2002/178/oj/eng>

¹¹ <https://www.coherentmarketinsights.com/industry-reports/food-traceability-market>

¹² <https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/4995280/food-traceability-market-global-forecast-2025>

¹³ <https://www.verifiedmarketresearch.com/product/food-traceability-software-market/>

¹⁴ Balakrishnan R, Zhang Y, Li H. A survey on machine learning methods for food safety risk assessment. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*. 2025;135:110960.

¹⁵ Chen X, Liu Y, Wang J. Analysis of food safety based on machine learning. *Food Chemistry*. 2025;448:137123.

¹⁶ Adewumi OO, Singh P, Rao S. Food Safety Prediction System: A Machine Learning Approach to Determining Safe Food Consumption. *Int J Innov Res Comput Sci Technol*. 2025;13(2):55–62.

¹⁷ Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). *Artificial Intelligence for Food Safety*. Rome: FAO; 2024.

controls^{14,15,16,18,19,20,21}. This preventive paradigm reinforces and extends HACCP-based food safety management by enabling dynamic risk scoring, targeted inspections, and more efficient allocation of control resources, thereby supporting safer products and more resilient supply chains for consumers and regulators alike^{17,19,20,22,23,24}.

In the earlier version of this deliverable, the analysis centred on three research papers (Nogales et al., 2022; Wu & Weng, 2021; Geng et al., 2022) that illustrated how machine learning methods can be applied to food risk prediction, often by exploiting regulatory datasets such as the EU Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF)^{14,23,24,25}. Since then, the scientific landscape has evolved rapidly, with new surveys on machine learning methods for food safety risk assessment, advanced AI-driven prediction frameworks using RASFF data, and transformer-based models for hazard detection and incident classification^{14,16,23,24,25}. This expanding evidence base, complemented by practice-oriented work on data analytics and digital technologies in food safety, confirms that a solution such as EFRA can generate substantial added value for food business operators, competent authorities, and researchers, while also providing a robust foundation for EFRA's go-to-market strategy, exploitation pathways, and sustainable business model^{17,18,19,23,24,25}.

4.2. External and Internal Analysis for EFRA

4.2.1. Overview

With the comprehensive market assessment completed across data-driven platforms, food safety risk and fraud prediction, and sector-specific domains, this section synthesises external and internal dimensions through PESTLE and SWOT frameworks. These analytical tools provide essential insights for strategic positioning, identifying key opportunities and threats in the broader environment, whilst simultaneously evaluating EFRA's internal capabilities and constraints. This dual analysis is instrumental in designing robust, contextualised business models aligned with stakeholder needs and regulatory realities.

4.2.2. External Environmental Analysis: PESTLE Framework

The macro-environmental landscape for data-driven food safety platforms is shaped by interconnected political, economic, sociocultural, technological, legal, and environmental forces. A PESTLE analysis (Table 13) captures these dimensions and informs EFRA's market adaptation strategy.

¹⁸ Motzer N, et al. Food safety related data analytics, digital, and artificial intelligence technologies. *Food Protection Trends*. 2024;44(11):437–447.

¹⁹ Jaiswal A, Kumar P. Data analytics in food safety: Improving quality control and risk management. *Current Journal of Applied Science and Technology*. 2025;44(4):1–14.

²⁰ Zhang L, Huang R, Sun D-W. Artificial intelligence for food safety: From predictive models to intelligent decision support. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*. 2025;143:105123.

²¹ Van der Fels-Klerx HJ, et al. Risk classification of food incidents: Development of a risk evaluation matrix for AI-supported decision-making. *Foods*. 2024;13(11):1785.

²² Kuo Y, Park J, Lee S. Advancing food safety through artificial intelligence: A detailed review of monitoring and detection technologies. *Food Science & Nutrition*. 2025;13(10):e70050.

²³ Niu B, Zhou Y, Li X. AI-driven food safety risk prediction: A transformer-based approach. *British Food Journal*. 2025;127(9):3427–3445.

²⁴ University of Portsmouth & IFST. AI-driven Risk Assessment in Food Safety Using EU RASFF Database. Technical Report. University of Portsmouth; 2025.

²⁵ Primority. Predictive Analytics in Food Safety: Preventing Contamination Before It Happens. White Paper; 2025.

Table 13: PESTLE analysis for EFRA as a data-driven food safety platform (updated 2025)

Dimension	Key Factors	Implications for EFRA
Political	EU and national authorities (EFSA, DG SANTE) promote data-driven, risk-based food safety management and digital transformation in official controls ^{26,27} .	Strong policy alignment for EFRA as an enabler of data-driven risk assessment, early warning, and regulatory decision support.
	FDA, EFSA and other agencies increasingly collaborate with industry and technology providers on AI, data-sharing and predictive analytics pilots ²⁸ .	Opportunity to position EFRA as trusted infrastructure in public-private partnerships and regulatory pilots.
	EU Digital Europe Programme and Green Deal incentivise digital, green and data-intensive solutions in the agri-food sector ²⁶ .	Supports funding, adoption and policy visibility for EFRA's green, AI-based platform.
Economic	AI in food safety market valued at ~USD 9.10 billion in 2025, projected to ~USD 68.80 billion by 2034 (CAGR ≈ 25.2%) ²⁹ .	Large and fast-growing addressable market for EFRA's AI-enabled risk analytics and data services.
	Food safety software and digital food safety management systems show robust growth (≈12% CAGR), with cloud-based deployments gaining share ^{30,31} .	Cloud-native EFRA architecture aligns with market demand for scalable, subscription-based models.
	Rising labour (≈4–6% increase) and logistics costs (+15% transport cost in Q1 2024) create pressure on margins and efficiency ³² .	EFRA can position its predictive capabilities to reduce incident-related losses and compliance costs.
Sociocultural	Around 70% of consumers indicate willingness to pay more for ethically sourced and traceable food products ³² .	Strengthens demand for traceability, transparency and risk intelligence services that EFRA can provide.
	Growing societal expectations for sustainability, animal welfare and responsible supply chains ³³ .	EFRA's green computing approach and risk prevention focus support corporate ESG narratives.

²⁶ European Commission & European Food Safety Authority. Digital Europe Programme and EU Green Deal: Strategic Priorities for Food Safety and Digitalisation. 2024-2025.

²⁷ European Food Safety Authority. Consolidated Annual Activity Report 2024. March 2025.

²⁸ Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Artificial Intelligence for Food Safety. Rome: FAO, 2024

²⁹ Towards FnB Research. AI in Food Safety Market Size, Growth, and Trends 2025 to 2034. September 2025.

³⁰ DataInsights Market. Food Safety Software Market 2025-2033: Trends and Competitor Analysis. July 2024.

³¹ Wiley IADNS. Advancing Food Safety Through Artificial Intelligence: A Detailed Review of Monitoring and Detection Technologies. October 2025.

³² Canvas Business Model. PESTLE Analysis of Food Industry Supply Chains: Economic Factors. November 2024.

³³ Deloitte. Sustainability & Food - EU Regulatory Outlook 2025. July 2025.

	Increasing digital literacy and uptake of analytics in food businesses and authorities ^{34,35} .	Facilitates adoption of advanced analytics and AI modules embedded in EFRA.
Technological	Cloud-based architectures become dominant in food safety software; SaaS models reduce up-front CAPEX ^{30,36} .	EFRA’s green cloud HPC and modular SaaS-ready design are technologically aligned with market trends.
	AI and ML deliver high accuracy in quality and safety applications (defect detection up to 95% in industrial use cases) ³⁷ .	Validates EFRA’s focus on AI-driven risk prediction and anomaly detection.
	IoT sensors enable real-time environmental monitoring; blockchain increasingly used for traceability; NLP/GenAI extract insights from unstructured sources ^{30,38,39} .	EFRA can integrate these technologies in its Data Hub and Analytics Powerhouse to offer multi-modal, real-time intelligence.
Legal / Regulatory	Stricter EU and US food safety rules (e.g. FSMA, updated EU criteria for <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> in RTE foods) raise compliance demands ⁴⁰ .	EFRA’s tools help operators meet more demanding documentation, monitoring and preventive control requirements.
	Data protection frameworks (GDPR and related) require privacy-by-design for data processing and analytics ^{27,35} .	EFRA’s federated learning and privacy-preserving design are strong selling points for regulators and data holders.
	Increasing use of risk-based inspection and data-supported official controls ^{26,27} .	EFRA can support competent authorities in risk classification, prioritisation and surveillance.
Environmental	Agriculture uses ~70% of global freshwater withdrawals; climate change intensifies resource pressure ³² .	Demand for efficient, low-waste, risk-preventive systems aligns with EFRA’s green data and analytics paradigm.
	Sustainable packaging market grows from ~USD 340 billion (2024) to an expected ~USD 470 billion by 2027 ³² .	Sustainability-oriented businesses seek digital tools that also optimise safety and quality, opening markets for EFRA.
	Pressure to reduce energy use and emissions from IT infrastructure in line with EU Green Deal objectives ^{26,27} .	EFRA’s energy-efficient crawling, green cloud HPC and federated edge processing offer a competitive environmental advantage.

³⁴ European Food Safety Authority & European Commission. Modernising Food Safety Regulation: Role of AI and Data Analytics. 2025

³⁵ New Food Magazine. AI in Food Safety: Real-World Solutions from IAFP 2025. July 2025.

³⁶ Archive Market Research. Digital Food Safety Management System: 2025 Trends and Forecast. December 2025.

³⁷ IONI AI. How AI Is Transforming Food Safety. May 2025.

³⁸ Fi Europe. How AI, Blockchain and Digital Platforms Are Transforming Food Safety Transparency. November 2025.

³⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2021.108697>

⁴⁰ Research and Markets. Food Safety Testing - Global Market Report 2025. December 2024

4.2.3. Internal Analysis: EFRA Strengths and Weaknesses

The external environment for data-driven food safety platforms is complex and dynamic. Understanding regulatory shifts, market trends, and competitive pressures helps organisations anticipate key opportunities and threats, which we capture systematically in a SWOT analysis.

SWOT analysis brings together what an organisation does well (strengths) and where it faces challenges (weaknesses) with what the market offers (opportunities) and what could go wrong (threats). Consider a food safety technology company: it might have cutting-edge AI expertise and innovative solutions, but limited brand recognition and tight budgets. Meanwhile, the market is hungry for digital transformation tools and regulators are pushing for advanced risk management. Yet well-funded competitors already have customer relationships and market share.

The real value of SWOT is straightforward: match your strengths to market opportunities. If your unique capabilities solve real problems customers face, you win. But SWOT also exposes uncomfortable truths, such as skills you lack and resources you need, especially in areas where external threats loom large. Smart strategy therefore focuses on what you do best, protects yourself against genuine risks, fixes weaknesses that matter most, and builds partnerships or secures funding where you're stretched thin. In practical terms, this means targeting customer segments where you have real advantage, investing strategically in areas under competitive pressure, and knowing when to collaborate rather than go it alone.

The following SWOT analysis (Table 14) is an update of the one performed in D6.2.1.

Table 14: SWOT Analysis of EFRA

ANALYSIS OBJECTIVES	
Based on everything discussed so far, identify the main strengths and opportunities that are going to help in establishing EFRA as a credible data platform for food safety/food risk prediction, penetrate the market and overcome operational challenges and external threats.	
INTERNAL FACTORS	
STRENGTHS +	WEAKNESSES –
<p><u>Novel NLU approaches published in peer-reviewed journals/conferences:</u> Food safety data appear in a variety of languages making the use of multilingual NLU approaches important. The state of the art of multilingual NLU exploits techniques based on pre-trained deep neural language models.</p> <p><u>Personalised AI Models:</u> The first-level training on public and private aggregated data allows for personalised AI models, potentially leading to more accurate predictions for MOY and other companies.</p> <p><u>Collaborative Training:</u> Engaging multiple food companies in the second-level federated learning approach can result in a robust and comprehensive AI model.</p>	<p><u>Interoperability:</u> Ensuring that data from different sources and sensors can be effectively integrated into the AI models may be technically challenging.</p> <p><u>Resource and Technical Challenges:</u> Developing and maintaining the infrastructure, tools, and technology required for two-level training and cloudlet applications can be resource-intensive.</p> <p><u>Data Quality:</u> Data quality is crucial for training accurate AI models. Inaccurate or incomplete data can lead to unreliable predictions. Extra care must be given at the data gathering and initial development stages to ensure optimal results.</p> <p><u>Data Privacy Concerns:</u> While privacy-preserving approaches are a strength, they may also introduce</p>

<p><u>Privacy-Preserving Approach:</u> The EFRA privacy-preserving two-level training approach ensures the protection of sensitive data, a significant advantage when dealing with healthcare and sensitive data like poultry pathogen information.</p> <p><u>Access to Data:</u> Leveraging the AGROKNOW and SGS Digicomply customer base provides access to valuable data sources for model training.</p> <p><u>Energy Efficient by design:</u> By design, EFRA incorporates green cloud HPC infrastructure and optimisation algorithms, reducing computational overhead compared to siloed, redundant crawling by individual organisations. This environmental advantage resonates with regulatory bodies and large enterprises committed to sustainability targets.</p>	<p>complexity and challenges in data handling, particularly when engaging external companies.</p> <p><u>Market Awareness and Brand Recognition:</u> As a nascent platform emerging from research and innovation funding, EFRA lacks the brand prominence of established food safety software vendors or specialised AI consultancies. Building market awareness requires sustained communication and early customer engagement.</p> <p><u>Data Access and Governance Complexity:</u> Whilst federated learning mitigates privacy concerns, negotiating data-sharing agreements with food companies and securing access to proprietary datasets remain operationally complex and time-consuming. Legal and contractual frameworks for cross-organisational data collaboration are still evolving.</p> <p><u>Commercialisation and Revenue Model Maturity:</u> Whilst EFRA has identified KERs and outlined potential business models, translating these into sustainable, recurring revenue streams requires iterative validation with customers and refinement of pricing strategies. SaaS models for food safety platforms are still establishing market norms.</p> <p><u>Dependency on Federated Learning Adoption:</u> EFRA's competitive advantage relies partly on acceptance and adoption of federated learning approaches by food companies. Regulatory and contractual uncertainties around federated learning (e.g., data leakage risks at client nodes) may slow adoption in risk-averse organisations.</p>
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EXTERNAL FACTORS	
OPPORTUNITIES +	THREATS –
<p><u>Expanding Market for AI-Driven Food Safety:</u> The projected USD 25.2% CAGR in the AI food safety market through 2034 provides substantial growth potential. Early positioning in this market enables EFRA to establish itself as a thought leader and trusted provider.</p> <p><u>Regulatory Mandates for Advanced Risk Prediction:</u> Evolving EU and global food safety regulations increasingly expect organisations to demonstrate proactive, data-driven risk management. EFRA's predictive analytics capabilities directly enable</p>	<p><u>Data Ownership/Liability Issues:</u> Clarifying data ownership and usage rights can be challenging when working with external companies.</p> <p><u>Cybersecurity threats:</u> The threat of cyber-attacks is constant for each organisation that moves operations online, much more for a data platform that contains sensitive private data.</p> <p><u>Competitive Emergence and Market Consolidation:</u> Established food safety software vendors (e.g., Fishbowl, Odo, specialist compliance platforms) are actively integrating AI and analytics capabilities. Large cloud providers (AWS, Azure, Google Cloud) are also</p>

<p>regulatory compliance and differentiate adopters from competitors.</p> <p><u>Data Collaboration Ecosystems and Industry Consortia:</u> Industry initiatives such as the Food Industry Intelligence Network (FIIN), which already encompasses over 70 member companies, demonstrate growing appetite for aggregated, anonymised data sharing for collective risk management. EFRA's Marketplace architecture aligns with this emerging ecosystem.</p> <p><u>CloudSaaS Market Expansion:</u> Cloud-based software adoption in food safety is accelerating, particularly among SMEs seeking cost-effective, scalable solutions without capital-intensive on-premises infrastructure. EFRA's cloud-native design positions it competitively.</p> <p><u>Regulatory Agency Partnerships:</u> Direct engagement with FDA, EFSA, and national authorities creates opportunities for EFRA to become strategic infrastructure for regulatory decision support, as evidenced by ongoing FDA collaborations with technology developers.</p> <p><u>Environmental Sensor Integration:</u> Incorporating environmental sensor data can enhance the predictive capabilities and broaden the scope of the AI model.</p> <p><u>Data literacy increase and ongoing digitisation of processes:</u> As workforces become better trained in data handling/analysis and as everyday processes are digitised, companies are more likely to adopt data solutions for their problems.</p> <p><u>Increase public concerns and new regulations regarding food safety:</u> increase public demand for food safety and new stricter regulations, might force some producers to improve their traceability processes or adopt a more proactive approach regarding food safety.</p>	<p>developing vertical solutions for food safety. Direct competition could commoditise certain EFRA components or fragment market demand.</p> <p><u>Regulatory Uncertainty Around Federated Learning and Privacy:</u> Whilst federated learning is promising, vulnerabilities and regulatory interpretation remain nascent. Should regulators impose stricter controls on model update transfers between federated nodes, or should data protection authorities challenge specific federated approaches, EFRA's technical differentiation could be constrained.</p> <p><u>Data Access Barriers and Trust Deficits:</u> Some food companies, particularly small and medium producers, may be reluctant to share proprietary operational data (microbial testing results, processing parameters) due to concerns about competitive disadvantage or intellectual property leakage. Building sufficient trust to achieve critical mass in data aggregation is a sustained challenge.</p> <p><u>Implementation and Adoption Friction:</u> Complex integration with existing enterprise systems, need for internal capability building, and organisational change management can delay adoption. Cost and time to realise value may deter risk-averse or resource-constrained operators.</p>
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4.2.4. Strategic Implications and Next Steps

This external and internal analysis affirms that EFRA operates in a favourable macroeconomic environment characterised by strong regulatory drivers, expanding market demand, and technological tailwinds. EFRA's technical architecture, consortium positioning, and alignment with regulatory modernisation represent significant competitive advantages. However, realising these advantages requires disciplined execution on market awareness, customer engagement, and evidence generation through use-case validation.

The following priorities support EFRA's transition from pilot to commercial deployment:

- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Deepen regulatory partnerships with FDA and EFSA to secure formal endorsement and pilot opportunities; establish early-adopter relationships with large food manufacturers willing to co-validate solutions.

- **Risk Mitigation:** Invest in enterprise-grade cybersecurity, transparent data governance frameworks, and legal templates to reduce barriers to data-sharing agreements.
- **Capability Development:** Build internal product, commercial, and customer success teams equipped to manage the complexity of federated learning deployments and multi-stakeholder coordination.
- **Evidence Generation:** Complete use-case validation cycles with rigorous performance metrics, cost-benefit analyses, and regulatory impact assessments to support marketing and sales processes.
- **Ecosystem Positioning:** Actively participate in industry consortia (FIIN, EREN frameworks) and standards-setting bodies to influence regulatory norms and secure preferential positioning in emerging data-sharing ecosystems.

4.3. Market analysis of Poultry Industry (linked Use Case #1)

In the previous deliverable (D6.2.2), a market analysis of the poultry industry was carried out. This section presents the most recent updates available up to the time of preparation of the present deliverable (D6.2.3).

Europe's poultry sector remains one of the world's most significant, with the EU producing roughly 14 million tonnes of meat annually and consistently ranking among the top three global exporters, alongside Brazil and the United States. The sector encompasses multiple production streams: broiler chicken for meat, layer hens for table eggs, and breeding flocks for hatcheries. Poland dominates EU production with 21% of total output, followed by Spain (13%), France (12%), Germany (11%), and Italy (10%)⁴¹.

Production has been climbing steadily. Output grew by approximately 5% in 2024 compared to 2023, and continued momentum is expected into 2025 and beyond, driven by sustained consumer demand and improving economic conditions across member states. This growth trajectory is particularly pronounced in countries like Romania, Poland, and Hungary, where new investments in processing and farming infrastructure are taking shape⁴².

Looking at the bigger picture, global poultry demand remains robust. The worldwide market, valued at roughly USD 350 billion in 2025, is expected to reach approximately USD 620 billion by 2034, expanding at a steady 6.6% annually. This growth reflects a fundamental consumer preference: poultry offers an affordable, lean protein source with a relatively lower environmental footprint compared to beef or pork—making it attractive in both developed and emerging markets⁴³.

Within this landscape, disease prevention has become critically important. The poultry diagnostics market—tools and tests used to detect pathogens like avian influenza and Newcastle disease early—is expanding rapidly. Currently valued at around USD 720 million in 2025, the diagnostics market is projected to grow to approximately USD 1.9 billion by 2035, at a 10% annual rate. Early detection systems help prevent costly outbreaks, reduce bird mortality, and protect both farm economics and export markets. Investments in molecular testing technologies, rapid diagnostic kits, and laboratory infrastructure are accelerating as regulators and producers recognise that prevention is far cheaper than managing disease crises⁴⁴.

4.4. Market analysis for Crop Farming (linked Use Case #2)

Agriculture sits at the heart of the global economy, a sector fundamentally reshaped by technological innovation, sustainability pressures, and shifting consumer demand. Globally, the agricultural market reached approximately USD 5.3 trillion in 2024 and is projected to grow to USD 16.8 trillion by 2029, reflecting

⁴¹ European Commission Agriculture Dashboard. EU Poultry Meat Broiler Production Data 2024. DG AGRI, 2025.

⁴² Zootecnica International. EU Poultry Market in 2024: Production Rebound, Stable Imports and Export Growth. March 2025.

⁴³ Yahoo Finance & Globe Newswire. Global Poultry Market Size, Share, Trends, Analysis, and Forecast 2025–2034. June 2025.

⁴⁴ Future Market Insights. Poultry Diagnostics Market Size & Industry Trends 2025–2035. June 2025.

a steady 6.6% annual expansion. This growth is underpinned by rising investment in precision agriculture technologies, genetic improvements in crop varieties, and expanding organic farming practices—all responses to mounting pressure on food security and environmental sustainability⁴⁵.

In the European Union, crop farming commands roughly half of total agricultural output. In 2024, EU crop production generated an estimated EUR 267.7 billion, representing 50.3% of the bloc's overall agricultural production value of EUR 531.9 billion. While cereal crops remain dominant—with wheat, maize, and barley as the primary commodities—the sector is increasingly diversified, encompassing oilseeds, protein crops, and specialty vegetables that respond to evolving dietary patterns and climate conditions. EU crop production recovered modestly in 2024-2025 after weather-related challenges the previous year, with cereals production forecast to increase roughly 11% and oilseeds showing resilience despite area contractions in sunflower and soybean plantings⁴⁶.

The structure of EU farming reflects a deeply rooted tradition of family ownership. Across the bloc's 9.1 million agricultural holdings, family farms account for approximately 94% of all farms, defined as operations where family members provide at least 50% of the regular labour force. This predominance of family farming is nearly universal, though France and Estonia stand out with sizeable non-family farm populations of 42% and 34%, respectively. The EU farm landscape also reveals stark economic stratification: roughly 3.3 million farms, about one-third of the total, generate less than EUR 2,000 in annual output and contribute only 1% to the sector's total economic value. These subsistence-oriented operations typically consume more than half their own production. At the opposite end, approximately 299,000 large agricultural enterprises—each producing EUR 250,000 or more annually—account for 56% of the sector's total economic output, demonstrating how concentrated productive capacity has become in the modern EU agricultural system⁴⁷.

4.5. Market analysis for Predictive Analytics in Regulatory Decisions (linked Use Case #3)

In the previous deliverable (D6.2.2), a market analysis of the poultry industry was carried out. This section presents the most recent updates available up to the time of preparation of the present deliverable (D6.2.3).

Predictive analytics is transforming how regulators and public authorities operate, shifting from reactive compliance checks to proactive, data-informed decision-making. Governments now leverage these tools to anticipate risks, optimise inspections, uncover patterns in compliance data, and evaluate policy impacts before implementation. Deloitte's 2025 analysis highlights how AI and predictive models are embedded across regulatory functions—from food safety surveillance to financial oversight—enabling more targeted, efficient, and transparent governance⁴⁸.

The market reflects this momentum. Valued at USD 10.2 billion in 2023, predictive analytics is forecast to reach USD 63.3 billion by 2032, growing at over 22% annually. Public sector adoption is accelerating due to vast data availability, cloud scalability, and accessible AI platforms that let agencies blend historical records with live feeds for real-time insights⁴⁹.

Challenges persist, though. Shifting data privacy rules and legacy IT systems demand ongoing model adjustments, while ensuring transparency and fairness remains critical for high-stakes decisions. Forward-

⁴⁵ Research and Markets & The Business Research Company. Agriculture Global Market Report 2025–2029. December 2024 and April 2025.

⁴⁶ European Commission Eurostat. Agricultural Economic Accounts 2024 - Crops Production Value. November 2024.

⁴⁷ European Commission Eurostat. Farms and Farmland in the European Union – Statistics (2020 Census). December 2021.

⁴⁸ Deloitte. (2025). The government and public services AI dossier. Deloitte Insights.

⁴⁹ Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2025). Regulating for the future: OECD regulatory policy outlook 2025. OECD Publishing.

thinking regulators are thus combining advanced analytics with strong governance, multidisciplinary oversight, and clear accountability to ensure these tools enhance, rather than supplant, human expertise⁵⁰.

4.6. Market Analysis for Mycotoxins in Animal Feed and Effects on Animal Production (linked Use Case #4)

Mycotoxins are among the most critical hidden risks in animal feed, particularly in poultry production, where even low-level, chronic exposure can reduce growth rates, impair immunity, and increase mortality. Global surveillance data consistently show high mycotoxin occurrence in key feed ingredients such as maize, wheat, and oilseed meals, with multiple toxins (e.g. aflatoxins, ochratoxin A, fumonisins, and Fusarium toxins) frequently co-occurring in the same batch. This co-contamination amplifies health impacts and complicates risk management, especially in intensive poultry systems where feed conversion efficiency and flock health are tightly linked to economic performance.

The economic relevance of mycotoxin control is reflected in the rapid growth of the testing and monitoring market. The global mycotoxin feed-testing market is estimated at around USD 1.54 billion in 2025 and is projected to reach approximately USD 2.31 billion by 2030, growing at about 8.6% annually, driven by stricter regulations, increased awareness of feed safety, and the need to protect high-value livestock sectors such as poultry⁵¹. When considering broader mycotoxin testing across food and feed, the market is valued at roughly USD 2.13 billion in 2025 and expected to grow to about USD 3.22 billion by 2031, at a CAGR of just over 7%, underpinned by climate-driven shifts in fungal prevalence and tighter enforcement of maximum residue limits in the EU and other major markets⁵².

For poultry and other monogastric species, mycotoxin exposure translates directly into reduced productivity and higher veterinary and management costs, making prevention and early detection a strategic priority for integrators, feed manufacturers, and regulators. In the EU, where compound feed production for poultry represents a substantial share of the overall feed market, compliance with mycotoxin limits is essential to safeguard both animal health and export competitiveness. Against this backdrop, solutions that combine continuous monitoring, predictive analytics, and targeted decision support, such as those developed in Use Case #4, are well positioned within a growing global market for mycotoxin risk management in animal feed, with relevance for high-intensity poultry value chains.

⁵⁰ Deloitte. (2025). Delivering on the promise of AI in government: Scaling AI in the public sector. Deloitte Insights.

⁵¹https://www.thebusinessresearchcompany.com/report/mycotoxin-feed-testing-global-market-report?utm_source=copilot.com

⁵²https://www.thebusinessresearchcompany.com/report/mycotoxin-feed-testing-global-market-report?utm_source=copilot.com

5. Business Models Playbook

This chapter plays a central role in the report by outlining key approaches and practical perspectives on the development of business models. Building on the content already presented in deliverable D6.2.2, it provides updated insights reflecting recent developments. In a rapidly changing market context, the ability to design and adjust business models is critical to long-term viability. The playbook reviews established business model approaches and highlights relevant factors to support EFRA partners in addressing external challenges. It serves as a practical reference to strengthen business planning, encourage innovation, and support the uptake of new market opportunities.

5.1. Business model development methodology

A detailed description of the business model development methodology is provided in deliverable D6.2.2.

5.2. Business model tools

In the previous versions of this deliverable (D6.2.1 and D6.2.2), a thorough review and benchmarking of existing business model tools was carried out to identify the most suitable approach for describing the value proposition of each use case. That analysis concluded that the Business Model Canvas (already detailed in the earlier iteration) remains the most effective method for illustrating each use case's value proposition, identifying market opportunities, and outlining strategies for delivering them. The Business Model Canvas emphasizes creating value for customers through products and services.

To avoid repetition, the business model canvases for the three use cases presented in the previous deliverable (D6.2.1) will not be reproduced here.

While EFRA has chosen to adopt the collaborative business model tool developed by DSSC⁵³ (see section 6.3) for data spaces, insights from the earlier Business Model Canvases continue to provide valuable guidance. These insights support the design and refinement of the DSSC tool, ensuring alignment with the strategic objectives and operational requirements identified in previous iterations.

5.3. Collaborative Business Model for the EFRA Platform

In earlier deliverables, the EFRA project applied the Business Model Canvas (BMC) to design and assess its use cases, benefiting from its simplicity and structured format. However, the growing complexity of data-driven business models and the emergence of data spaces highlighted the need for a more specialized approach. The Collaborative Business Model tool, developed by DSSC, offers a dynamic alternative tailored to the unique requirements of data-centric platforms, making it particularly suitable for EFRA's evolving needs.

Unlike the traditional BMC, which supports general business model development, the DSSC tool is designed to capture the complex interactions between data providers, consumers, and intermediaries. This is especially relevant for EFRA, where data flows and value exchanges are central to the use cases. The tool enables detailed mapping of data governance, monetization strategies, and compliance requirements, addressing gaps that the BMC does not fully cover in such contexts.

The DSSC Collaborative Business Model tool also integrates with current data space principles, including interoperability, sovereignty, and trust. EFRA's use cases, offered services, and the EFRA Marketplace, which depend on secure data exchange among stakeholders, benefit from this alignment. By facilitating a

⁵³ <https://dssc.eu/>

structured analysis of roles and responsibilities in data sharing, the tool ensures that EFRA’s business models comply with European initiatives such as Gaia-X and the European Data Strategy, building on the foundations laid in the previous deliverables.

5.3.1. Workshop on the Validation and Users Contribution to the Collaborative Business Model and EFRA Sustainability

In the previous deliverable (D6.2.2) we described how the EFRA consortium reached to a consensus about the use of the DSSC Business Model Development Tool. In summary, on November 26th, RAINNO hosted a workshop during EFRA’s plenary meeting in Athens to discuss and evaluate the new DSSC Business Model Development Tool and its role in supporting the sustainability of the EFRA platform. Consortium partners explored the tool through interactive sessions using real EFRA use cases, identifying its benefits for mapping data flows, governance, and value creation. The workshop concluded with a consensus to adopt the tool for EFRA’s business model development. The concluded EFRA Business Model Canvas is presented in D6.2.2.

In the EFRA Business Model Canvas, some fields were intentionally left open to be defined at a later stage. The consortium agreed to organise an additional round of user validation and input once the project reached a higher level of maturity, ensuring that the revised model is aligned with current market needs.

Thus, on 21 October 2025, RAINNO hosted a workshop during Synergy Days 2025 in Rotterdam⁵⁴ titled “Business models for AI-powered platforms in bioeconomy and food chains”, co-organised with the Horizon Europe project ARGONAUT, in which RAINNO is also a partner⁵⁵ (Figure 3). During this workshop, RAINNO presented the EFRA project, showcased the EFRA Business Model Canvas and engaged participants in an in-depth discussion on its soundness and potential updates.

Figure 3: Workshop titled “Business models for AI-powered platforms in bioeconomy and food chains”, co-organized by EFRA during Synergy Days 2025.

Organising a dedicated workshop during the Synergy Days is crucial for validating the EFRA Business Model Canvas, as it places the project at the heart of Europe’s digital innovation ecosystem. By engaging directly

⁵⁴ <https://www.synergyportal.eu/synergy-days>

⁵⁵ https://www.synergyportal.eu/synergy-days/2025/synergy-days-2025_workshop-tracks.pdf (page 3)

with policymakers, researchers, SMEs, Digital Innovation Hubs, and Agri-tech practitioners, the workshop enabled real-world feedback on value propositions, market needs, scalability, and regulatory alignment. Participants were invited to suggest **Enabling Services** and the corresponding **Value Proposition** (two of the missing fields in the earlier EFRA Business Model Canvas), allowing the consortium to complete the remaining fields of the Business Model Canvas. Furthermore, the interactive setting gives the opportunity to the consortium to test assumptions, refine their business strategy, and identify potential partners or early adopters, ensuring the business model is robust, market-oriented, and aligned with the evolving digital transformation of the European agri-food sector.

The most popular are presented in Table 15. These contributions were subsequently reviewed by the consortium and, together with other refinements introduced over the past year, were incorporated into the updated EFRA Business Model Canvas (Figure 4).

Table 15: Results of Users' answers during the workshop in Synergy Days 2025.

Enabling Service	Votes
Cloud & HPC Infrastructure Providers	5
Data Management & Integration Providers	13
Security & Compliance Providers	7
IoT and Sensor Data Providers	4
Standardization & Certification Bodies	7
Other	0

Value Proposition	Votes
New Market Access & Exposure / Revenue Generation via Integration	7
Co-innovation Opportunities	2
Long-term Partnerships within EFRA Ecosystem	7
Enhanced Data Utility	11
Trust & Compliance Branding	8
Other	0

6. Impact

The EFRA project addresses a critical intersection of European policy priorities: safeguarding food systems through advanced data analytics whilst simultaneously advancing the European data economy and digital transformation. Operating within the EU's commitment to the Farm to Fork Strategy and the broader European Green Deal, EFRA demonstrates how artificial intelligence and predictive analytics can serve as strategic tools for building more resilient, transparent, and sustainable food supply chains.

This section builds upon the impact narrative developed progressively through D6.2.1 and D6.2.2, integrating final validation evidence and demonstrating how EFRA's matured portfolio of KERs, robust business models, and durable sustainability framework positions the project for sustained contribution to European food systems and data ecosystems beyond formal project conclusion.

6.1. Systemic Contributions to Food Safety and Risk Prevention

As detailed extensively in D6.2.1 and D6.2.2, EFRA's four validated use cases demonstrate the operational feasibility and practical relevance of AI-driven predictive analytics in food safety contexts. The project has advanced these use cases from concept to real-world deployment, validating them under operational conditions at partner premises including MOY Park and Agrivi. This progression from theoretical model to working system constitutes a material contribution to EFSA's identified strategic priorities for accelerating risk assessment productivity and strengthening digital collaboration within the EU food safety system⁵⁶.

The federated learning and edge-based AI training architectures employed across EFRA's use cases address a foundational challenge in food industry data governance: the need for collective intelligence systems that do not require centralised data pooling. This technical approach is directly aligned with principles outlined in the European Data Strategy and governance frameworks anticipated for emerging data spaces⁵⁷. By demonstrating operationally viable implementations of these principles, EFRA provides evidence and practical models for broader adoption across sectors.

The business model framework articulated in D6.2.2 (Section 6) reveals how this technical foundation translates into sustainable, multi-stakeholder value creation. The evolution of EFRA's KER portfolio from three to nine results reflects not only the expanding technical scope of consortium achievements, but also the growing diversity of exploitation pathways now available to partners. These pathways are grounded in market-validated demand signals (see also D6.2.1).

6.2. Positioning Within the European Data Economy and Data Spaces Ecosystem

EFRA's maturation coincides with the EU's accelerated investment in Common European Data Spaces. The European Data Monitoring Tool confirms sustained market momentum: the EU data market expanded by 12.4% year-over-year to reach USD 92 billion in 2024, with projections indicating compound annual growth rates of 3.6–7.5% through 2030⁵⁸. Within this context, EFRA's domain-specific, operationally validated platform demonstrates how agricultural and food safety data can be leveraged for high-value predictive analytics whilst maintaining governance frameworks aligned with EU trust and transparency standards.

The EFRA Data Hub, documented in detail in D6.2.1 (Section 5.1.2), serves a dual purpose within the emerging data ecosystem. Commercially, it enables the EFRA Data & Analytics Marketplace to deliver curated analytical services to fee-paying users. Non-commercially, it functions as a shared infrastructure available to the

⁵⁶ EFSA (2024). Programming Document 2024-2026: Priorities for digital collaboration and risk assessment productivity in the EU food safety system.

⁵⁷ EFSA. (2024). EFSA Strategy 2027 – Mid-term review: Digital enablement, cooperation, and emerging risk assessment.

⁵⁸ European Commission. (2024). European Data Monitoring Tool. Data Economy Insights, EU27.

broader food safety research and innovation community, a role that amplifies EFRA's contribution to the building blocks of farm-centric European agricultural data spaces. This dual-pathway design exemplifies the business model innovation articulated in D6.2.2, wherein data-centric platforms generate value through orchestration of governance structures, trusted partnerships, and sustainable revenue models rather than through proprietary control of assets alone.

The automated regulatory analysis modules integrated into EFRA address a persistent information challenge documented in D6.2.1 market analysis: the volume and complexity of food safety legislation across jurisdictional boundaries. By automating analysis and summarisation of regulatory obligations from diverse EU and national frameworks, EFRA reduces administrative friction for producers and processors, particularly smaller enterprises with limited compliance resources. These efficiency gains create both direct cost benefits and indirect systemic strengthening of supply chain integrity.

6.3. Market Maturation and Stakeholder Adoption Pathways

The market analysis foundations established in D6.2.1 are substantiated by demonstrated industry adoption patterns. Blockchain-enabled traceability systems (closely complementary to EFRA's offerings) now operate at scale across thousands of companies, tracking hundreds of thousands of transactions daily. Global food safety solutions exhibit sustained expansion momentum. These industry trends validate the market opportunity assessment that informed EFRA's business model development in D6.2.2.

The sustainability framework outlined in D6.2.2 establishes multiple revenue pathways designed to reduce market concentration risk and enable adoption across heterogeneous user segments. The KERs portfolio documented in D6.2.2 spans infrastructure layers (EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, Data Hub), user-facing marketplaces (EFRA Data & Analytics Marketplace), and domain-specific predictive models (salmonella, pest dynamics, mycotoxins, regulatory assessment). Each KER carries a distinct Unique Value Proposition tailored to defined stakeholder groups, from farm operators and crop protection specialists to compliance officers and regulatory analysts.

This portfolio differentiation is particularly significant for sustainability beyond project funding. As detailed in D6.2.2, the business model encompasses subscription-based platform access, project-based consulting, licensing of proprietary models, and data enrichment services. This diversification distributes revenue risk and positions EFRA results for adoption across user segments with varying operational and financial profiles.

6.4. Multi-Stakeholder Value Creation and Impact Distribution

The stakeholder engagement and value articulation strategies developed in D6.2.2 extend EFRA's impact across the food supply chain. For producers, whether poultry farmers accessing salmonella risk prediction or crop producers receiving pest early-warning alerts, EFRA delivers quantifiable operational advantages: earlier risk detection, targeted intervention, and reduced losses from disease or pest damage. These producer benefits generate economic returns that reinforce adoption momentum.

For compliance and regulatory professionals, the automated regulatory analysis module addresses a documented compliance challenge: managing complex, multi-jurisdictional regulatory obligations with limited in-house analytical capacity. By providing machine-readable summaries and actionable compliance guidance, EFRA reduces manual effort and human error, thereby freeing regulatory expertise toward strategic planning and risk assessment rather than administrative burden.

For the research and analytics community, EFRA's infrastructure provides access to unprecedented volumes of curated, semantically harmonised food safety data, a resource that enables new research directions and accelerates methodological innovation. This non-commercial value pathway, articulated in D6.2.2, sustains demand for the platform's data discovery and analysis functions beyond commercial subscribers.

Consumers benefit through systemic improvements in food safety and supply chain transparency, outcomes that compound across the supply chain as producer-level risk prevention, regulatory compliance, and research-driven innovation reinforce one another.

6.5. Alignment with EU Strategic Frameworks

EFRA's positioning directly supports multiple EU policy objectives articulated in the Farm to Fork Strategy, European Green Deal, Digital Europe Programme, and EFSA's strategic planning documents⁵⁴.

Climate adaptation and agricultural sustainability: The project's emphasis on climate-relevant risk factors (such as temperature dynamics influencing pest population dynamics and mycotoxin-producing fungal growth) positions food safety analytics as a strategic tool for climate adaptation within agricultural systems. By enabling data-driven, targeted risk management, EFRA reduces reliance on broad-spectrum interventions (such as preventive pesticide applications) in favour of knowledge-based management tailored to specific risk profiles.

Digital governance and trusted data ecosystems: EFRA's implementation of federated learning and privacy-preserving edge-based AI training operationalises principles central to the Digital Europe Programme's investment in trustworthy data governance. By demonstrating working implementations in a domain of direct public interest, EFRA contributes evidence and practical models applicable to data space development across sectors.

Food system resilience and risk preparedness: The project's methodologies and analytical tools address EFSA's identified strategic priority for enhanced preparedness in emerging food risk assessment. As climate change, agricultural intensification, and globalised supply chains create novel food safety scenarios, the capabilities demonstrated through EFRA enhance the EU food safety system's capacity for rapid response and evidence-based decision-making.

6.6. Mechanisms for Impact Multiplication and Ecosystem Integration

The durability and multiplier effects of EFRA results are embedded in three structural design features.

First, the EFRA Data Hub functions as shared infrastructure available to complementary initiatives within the Horizon Europe food safety research portfolio, including projects such as HOLiFOOD and FoodSafeR. This design generates positive externalities beyond direct project outputs, amplifying contribution to emerging agricultural data space development.

Second, the consortium's adoption of the Collaborative Business Model Development Tool (D6.2.2) rather than traditional Business Model Canvas approaches reflects EFRA's integration into the emerging European data ecosystem architecture. This methodological evolution acknowledges that value creation in data-centric platforms arises not from proprietary control alone, but from the orchestration of governance structures, trusted partnerships, and sustainable revenue models that enable collective value generation.

Third, the consortium's commitment to a four-year post-project exploitation strategy, including defined IPR protection timelines and structured partnership development (see Section 4), ensures that impact trajectory extends well beyond formal project conclusion. This approach converts time-limited research funding into durable innovation infrastructure capable of sustaining benefits across multiple stakeholder cohorts and geographic regions.

7. Sustainability plan

The sustainability framework for EFRA has been developed incrementally across D6.2.1 and D6.2.2 and is finalised in this deliverable. Rather than re-stating the detailed marketing plans, financial templates and business canvases already presented, this section consolidates the main strategic choices and documents how the consortium will translate them into concrete governance, operational and financial arrangements after the end of the project. It should therefore be read as a continuation of the sustainability narrative initiated in D6.2.1 and refined in D6.2.2, now informed by the full maturity of the KER portfolio and the collaborative business model adopted in D6.2.3.

7.1. Sustainability Plan for Commercial Results

As described in D6.2.1 and updated in D6.2.2, the commercial sustainability of EFRA rests on a diversified portfolio of 9 KERs spanning infrastructure (EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, EFRA Data Hub), services (EFRA Data & Analytics Marketplace) and specialised AI models and tools (e.g. mycotoxin predictive models, Predictions Library, extreme event forecasting). The present section does not re-list their technical characteristics or UVPs, which are documented comprehensively in D6.2.2. Instead, it clarifies how these assets will be operated, governed and monetised over the four-year post-project period.

7.1.1. Financial projections and funding pathways

D6.2.1 introduced revenue, cost and profitability templates that support scenario-based financial planning for the EFRA platform and its commercial KERs. These templates have been further refined and populated during D6.2.2 and the final project year, using updated market figures from the European Data Market Monitoring Tool and recent sectoral studies on food safety analytics and traceability. Rather than reproducing these tables here, D6.2.3 confirms three overarching conclusions that underpin EFRA's sustainability outlook:

- the European data market and data economy continue to grow at robust rates, with the data market value in the EU27 increasing by 12.4% year-on-year to reach USD 92 billion in 2024, and projected compound annual growth rates of 3.6–7.5% through 2030, according to the European Commission's European Data Market Study 2024–2026,
- the food safety testing and traceability segments, summarised in D6.2.2 (Section 5), show sustained demand for predictive analytics and decision-support tools, with global food safety testing projected to grow at more than 7% CAGR and traceability software at over 10% CAGR over the current decade,
- the willingness of food system actors to invest in data-driven solutions has been reinforced by EU regulatory trajectories (for example, the Farm to Fork Strategy and the implementation of Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 on traceability) and by corporate commitments to risk management and ESG reporting.

Based on these inputs and the KER-specific exploitation intentions captured through the BFMULO matrix (D6.2.1 and D6.2.2), including the updated KER definitions introduced in this version of the deliverable, EFRA's commercial sustainability strategy is structured around three complementary revenue pillars:

- Platform revenues, primarily associated with the EFRA Data & Analytics Marketplace, and secondarily with the supporting EFRA Data & Analytics Powerhouse and EFRA Data Hub, where partners AGROKNOW, JAKALA, CNR, SU and WFSR have declared explicit roles as providers and operators. This includes revenue generated through front-end Marketplace services, where access to EFRA assets provided via third-party applications (e.g. EFRA decision-support tools available through AGROKNOW's FOODAKAI, SGS Digicomply or the Agrivi Farm Management System) may trigger referral fees returned to the Marketplace. These referral arrangements apply both to third-party software applications and to data APIs accessed through the Marketplace interface.

The validation workshops with food-industry stakeholders (as reported in D4.3.3) confirmed a general reluctance to openly share datasets or predictive AI models, while showing strong interest in accessing EFRA assets (datasets, decision-support tools, APIs and models). In this context, the Marketplace's ability to support private data-sharing networks, such as the Food Fortress network established under Use Case 4 and the F-MIN microbiology network described in D4.3.3, provides a viable mechanism for secure, anonymous and controlled data exchange among trusted members.

- **Service revenues**, mobilising EFRA tools and datasets within tailored consulting, risk-assessment or data-enrichment assignments for food businesses, regulators or research clients. This also includes direct revenues generated by third-party services (e.g. FOODAKAI, Agrivi, SGS Digicomply) when EFRA predictive AI models are integrated into their platforms to provide additional value-added services through their own commercial components.
- **Licensing and co-development arrangements**, where specific EFRA predictive AI models (e.g. the mycotoxin prediction model) are integrated into third-party platforms under licence or executed directly within the EFRA Powerhouse when no suitable third-party UI environment exists. In such cases, execution requires a prior step of API validation and configuration to ensure compatibility with EFRA components.

Furthermore, when new predictive models are submitted by external providers for integration and execution within the EFRA Powerhouse, a specific collaboration agreement will define the one-off integration fee and the associated execution and hosting conditions.

The detailed financial projections, including conservative, baseline and optimistic scenarios, remain in the annexes and templates of D6.2.1 and D6.2.2. D6.2.3 confirms that these scenarios have been revisited considering updated data-economy indicators and the updated KER portfolio, and remain viable, with the consortium converging on the baseline trajectory presented in D6.2.2 as the reference case for the first three post-project years.

From a funding perspective, the consortium will combine own revenues with targeted participation in new projects and calls to bridge the early post-project phase. As already indicated in D6.2.2, EFRA partners have identified relevant opportunities under Horizon Europe clusters, Digital Europe actions on common data spaces, and national or regional innovation schemes. For the early post-project period, all involved partners have agreed to allocate dedicated time to ensure the minimum level of maintenance required to keep the project outcomes operational. At the same time, third-party software applications that already integrate EFRA predictive AI models (such as AGROKNOW's FOODAKAI, SGS Digicomply and the Agrivi Farm Management System) will continue to maintain these components as part of their regular commercial operations, since these services are already embedded in their active product offerings.

D6.2.3 formalises this as a rolling pipeline, incorporating the updated KERs as core assets for future proposals. Each year, at least two joint funding applications will be prepared that explicitly build on EFRA assets, ensuring continuity of technical development and partial coverage of platform operating costs during the scale-up phase. The consortium will therefore maintain both options in parallel: (i) a baseline level of partner-funded maintenance to safeguard operational continuity, and (ii) the pursuit of new funding opportunities to accelerate further development and expansion.

7.1.2. Development

The marketing strategy first outlined in D6.2.1 and deepened in D6.2.2 already defines EFRA's mission, key messages, marketing mix and customer personas. Rather than revisiting those components, this final deliverable focuses on how they will be operationalised in practice.

The EFRA platform's mission and core narrative, "enabling proactive, AI-driven food risk management through trusted data and analytics", remains unchanged. What evolves in D6.2.3 is the degree of concreteness: the validated use cases and the expanded KER set allow the consortium to move from generic promises to specific, demonstrable outcomes (e.g. improved targeting of sampling campaigns, better alignment of pest alarms with climatic triggers, more efficient regulatory monitoring workflows). These

outcomes are already described in the use-case updates of D6.2.3 and will be systematically incorporated into marketing narratives as short case examples, without duplicating technical detail here.

On the operational side, three elements are central to commercial sustainability:

- Lead generation and relationship building will build on the customer personas identified in D6.2.2, particularly food manufacturers and integrators for Use Case #1, crop producers and digital agriculture providers for Use Case #2, compliance teams and regulatory bodies for Use Case #3, farmers and animal stock industry for Use Case #4. The consortium will prioritise relationship-based approaches (joint pilots, co-creation workshops, technical webinars) over mass marketing, reflecting the specialised and trust-sensitive nature of food safety analytics.
- Brand and positioning will continue to leverage EFRA's association with EU research excellence and the broader European data-space agenda. References to EFRA's alignment with the European Data Strategy, the Farm to Fork Strategy and EFSA's digitalisation priorities will be maintained in external communication, drawing on official Commission and EFSA documents rather than generic marketing language.
- Performance monitoring will use the tentative marketing KPIs proposed in D6.2.2 (for example, number of active platform users, number of commercial contracts signed, conversion rates from pilots to paid services) as the basis for a light monitoring dashboard. This dashboard will be maintained by RAINNO as coordinating partner and reviewed annually with the exploitation leads for key KERs.

In line with the principles of responsible innovation, particular attention will be paid to transparent communication about data governance, model limitations and risk management. This is consistent with European Commission guidance on trustworthy AI and data governance in the Digital Europe Programme and supports long-term trust and adoption.

7.1.3. Business Model Canvasses for Commercial Results

The business models initially designed and documented in the earlier iterations of this deliverable (D6.2.1 and D6.2.2) have been revisited, refined and consolidated in the present version to reflect the project's full set of validated use cases and the expanded portfolio of eight Key Exploitable Results. Rather than redefining the underlying logic, the current deliverable updates the previous canvasses to incorporate real-world feedback from piloting activities, the transition to the collaborative business model framework, and partners' final exploitation intentions, ensuring that the resulting models are directly usable as post-project blueprints. In the following subsections, the revised business model canvasses for the EFRA Platform and the individual commercial KERs are presented in their final form, building explicitly on the structures and assumptions laid out in the previous deliverables while providing a coherent and up-to-date foundation for the sustainability plan. Below you can find the updated and finalized Business Model Canvasses for:

- a. The EFRA Platform (Figure 4)
- b. Use Case #1 (Figure 5),
- c. Use Case #2 (Figure 6),
- d. Use Case #3 (Figure 7) and
- e. Use Case #4 (Figure 8).

7.2. Sustainability Plan for non-Commercial Results

D6.2.1 and D6.2.2 (Sections 8.2) already distinguish clearly between commercial KERs and non-commercial results that primarily serve scientific, educational or policy objectives. These include, for example, methodological advances in federated learning for food risk analytics, curated datasets and ontologies, and the collaborative business model methodology adapted from the DSSC framework. The role of D6.2.3 is not to re-describe these assets, but to clarify how they will continue to generate value beyond the project.

The non-commercial sustainability strategy rests on three main pillars:

- **Continued use and expansion of EFRA assets in research and innovation projects:** as noted in D6.2.2, several partners (AGROKNOW, WR, CNR, SU and others) plan to embed EFRA datasets, models and tools into future research proposals on topics such as agri-food data spaces, climate-related food risks and AI-assisted risk assessment. This ensures that EFRA outcomes remain living components of an evolving research portfolio rather than static deliverables.
- **Open and semi-open access to knowledge resources, in line with Horizon Europe's open science principles:** where compatible with IPR and confidentiality constraints, EFRA publications, methodological descriptions and high-level documentation of models and workflows will remain accessible via institutional repositories, the project website and partners' communication channels. This reflects the commitment to contribute to the wider European knowledge base on AI in food safety, as advocated by EFSA and the European Commission.
- **Capacity building and community engagement, leveraging the stakeholder relationships developed in WP6.** Training materials, webinars and workshop formats piloted during the project (e.g. the IPR workshops and the collaborative business model sessions described in D6.2.2) will be adapted for use in future projects, professional training courses or internal programmes of consortium partners.

From a governance perspective, the same post-project structures used for commercial sustainability (i.e. the exploitation leads for each KER and the coordinating role of RAINNO) will also oversee the stewardship of non-commercial outputs. Annual reviews of the KER catalogue and associated IP status, already foreseen in the post-project IPR strategy, will explicitly consider non-commercial impacts and opportunities for further use in policy support or scientific collaboration.

In this way, the sustainability plan for non-commercial results complements the commercial pathways and supports EFRA's broader mission: to strengthen Europe's capacity for evidence-based, data-driven food risk management, even in contexts where direct revenue generation is not the primary objective. These ideas are included in the Business Model Canvas for Non-Commercial Results (Figure 9).

7.2.1. Business Model Canvas for Non-Commercial Results

The updated and finalized Business Model Canvas for Non-Commercial Results can be seen in

Figure 9.

Principles, Scope, Objectives

Leveraging AI, big data, IoT, and HPC, the EFRA platform aims to lead in secure, green data platforms, fostering collaboration across the food supply chain, scaling predictive tools to address food risks and regulations, and creating a data marketplace that drives economic engagement between data providers and consumers.

Use Cases

- AI and data analytics to address food risks poultry pathogens (salmonella)
- AI and data analytics to optimize pesticide use to ensure food safety by predicting and managing pest risks effectively.
- Enhancing regulatory decisions with integrated food risk intelligence data for more effective food safety regulations

Value Added Service Providers

- Dimensions of data management and processing such as: data visualisation, quality, anonymisation, enrichment, selection, extraction, combination, processing, transformation, packaging.
- ML Models hosting, Federated Learning, Marketplace, AI
- Data fusion

Enabling Service Providers

- Cloud & HPC
- Infrastructure Providers
- Data Management & Integration Providers
- Security & Compliance Providers
- IoT and Sensor Data Providers
- Standardization & Certification Bodies

Value Proposition

Data Providers: Network expansion and data impact amplification. Secure and responsible data management. Unlock monetization opportunities with tailored solutions.

Data Recipients: Access high-quality, purpose-driven datasets. Simplify data integration and interoperability. Leverage curated data to fuel innovation and efficiency.

Users Using Analytics: Gain insights with advanced analytical tools. Drive decisions with data-driven strategies. Discover growth opportunities with aggregated data.

Value Proposition

- Access to AI-driven analytics for food safety risk management
- Secure data-sharing frameworks and collaborative tools to enhance decision-making
- Innovation through an open data ecosystem and predictive systems for solution development
- Opportunity to connect with a large user base of data space participants
- Tailored resources to optimize efficiency, scalability, and service delivery

Value Proposition

- New Market Access & Exposure / Revenue Generation via Integration
- Co-innovation Opportunities
- Long-term Partnerships within EFRA Ecosystem
- Enhanced Data Utility
- Trust & Compliance Branding

Pricing, Cost and Revenue Models

A Post-Free Period of 12 months. After the initial period, tech partners will calculate costs as a percentage of the total subscription fee (e.g., 1-2%). Upon reaching a critical number of subscriptions, the maintenance cost will transition to a SaaS model with an annual subscription fee.

Network Effects

- **Initial Free Access** (e.g) free trials and **Incentivized Participation** (e.g rewards for referrals) for all users with generous limits on API.
- **Tailored Outreach and Engagement** to engage key user groups (farmers, agronomists, researchers and academia) via industry fairs and journals, collaborations with networks, webinars and meetings.
- **Promoting Network Effects:**
 1. **Same-Side Network Effects:** (success stories and best practices for participants attraction. Community building of practice for sharing insights and fostering collaboration among stakeholders in similar fields.
 2. **Cross-Side Network Effects:** Attraction of value-added service providers with free or subsidized onboarding and emphasis on access to diverse datasets and stakeholders. Offer premium analytics tools or services to incentivize participation from both data providers and service users.
- **Building Trust and Scalability:**
 1. Establish robust data governance frameworks to ensure privacy, security, and compliance.
 2. Gradually shift from free trials to paid models as the ecosystem matures, ensuring sustainability.

Data Space

Value Proposition

Financial (monetised rewards/cost reductions) and Operational (exclusive access/ Networking/Capacity building) benefits for entities. Clear Accountability Structures for entities (defined roles and responsibilities/Performance metrics/Monitoring and Reporting mechanisms/Code of conduct and compliance/Conflict resolution processes

Participants in Governance Authority

Currently, for-profit entities like Value-Added Service Providers and Technical Operators from the EFRA consortium with IPR on reusable infrastructure or modules. Future members must align with EFRA's objectives, contribute value, and adhere to data governance policies. Membership will be open to qualified entities based on their ability to support EFRA's goals.

Resources and Activities

Resources: Data governance frameworks, technical infrastructure for secure data sharing, and standardized protocols.

Activities: Compliance monitoring, participant support and training, continuous feedback loops, and stakeholder engagement to ensure system efficiency, adaptability, and interoperability.

Governance

- 2-Level Governance:
1. For-profit EFRA entities in the consortium that have IPR on re-usable parts of the infrastructure and/or modules/models with shares
 2. Not-for-profit EFRA entities that can act as an Internal Advisory board offering scientific advices in related matters

Monitoring

- **Feedback Mechanisms** through regular engagement with stakeholders (data providers, participants, and users) ensuring that the business model reflects current needs and expectations.
- **Performance Monitoring** by the governance authority overseeing operational and financial performance metrics, ensuring that the business model aligns with objectives and adapts to market changes.
- **Scenario Analysis** for periodic evaluation of market trends and regulatory developments to anticipate possible shifts that might necessitate business model adjustments.

Business Model Innovation Process

- **Continuous Stakeholder Engagement:** Regular feedback from users, participants, and providers to identify shifts in needs and preferences.
- **Performance Monitoring:** Analyzing KPIs and market trends to identify areas and align with business goals, prompting redesigns.
- **Change Management:** A robust change management process to ensure the EFRA platform can effectively respond to feedback and external shifts, enabling quick adaptations without disrupting operations.

Figure 4: EFRA Business Model Development Canvas (updated).

Business Model for EFRA		<i>Designed for:</i> Stakeholders in Poultry Industry		
<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data providers (data vendors, government agencies, or other businesses in related industries) • Academics & Research organisations • Standardization Bodies • Governments and Regulatory Agencies 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Mining and Data Aggregation (especially in poultry) • A.I. models training and optimization, especially in risk prediction for poultry pathogens • Store Data • Annotate Data <p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personnel Expertise • Partner Expertise • Public Data Sources • Private Data Source 	<p>Value Propositions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased Prediction Accuracy • Relevant industries have significant size, and they are projected to keep growing • Cloud-based platform provides advanced decision-making tools (KER1). • A user-friendly web app that allows discovery and purchase / use of raw data and analytics services (KER2). • Industry expertise and experience 	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website and online portal • Direct Portal/Customer support • User friendly services through the Marketplace • Customer or User Communities (engage for feedback and insights) <p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Online customer portal • Social Media • Indirect Sales thought leadership publications (Scientific, Technical, White paper etc.) • Workshops/Webinars • Direct Sales 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poultry Farm Owners • Poultry Processing Companies • Academics & Research organisations • Poultry importers and exporters
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technologies and Intellectual properties development • Online platform’s development and maintenance • Data acquisition • Partnerships management • Personnel • Sales & Marketing Activities • Certification and Compliance (ISO) 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subscription based fee 		

Figure 5: Business Model Canvas (updated) for Use Case #1

Business Model for EFRA		Designed for: Stakeholders in Crops Industry		
<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data providers (data vendors, government agencies, or other businesses in related industries) • Technology providers (cloud infrastructure, data storage, data processing, and analytics tools) • Academics & Research organisations • Cyber Security Partners • Customer or User Communities (engage for feedback and insights) • Governments and Regulatory Agencies 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Mining and Data Aggregation for pesticide use data • Ensure access to data (public and private) • A.I. models training and optimization, especially for pesticide use optimization • Insure efficiency and interoperability of the systems • Pest outbreak data • Predictions • Provide metadata 	<p>Value Propositions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevant industries have significant size, and they are projected to keep growing • Cloud-based platform provides advanced decision-making tools (KER1). • A user-friendly web app that allows discovery and purchase / use of raw data and analytics services (KER2). • A Data Hub enriched with anonymized corporate data sets and supply chain data streams (KER3). • Industry expertise and experience • Offer pest outbreak prediction • Pest appearance criteria database • Decision making tools on advanced platform 	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website and online portal • Direct Portal/Customer support • User friendly services through the Marketplace • EFRA Marketplace (used buy/sell data + models) • Web App 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop Farmers • Crop Processing Companies • Governments and Regulatory Agencies • Academics & Research organisations • Crop importers and exporters • Key partners: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Farmers - Food processing companies - Agronomists
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technologies and Intellectual properties development • Online platform’s development and maintenance • Data acquisition and storage costs • Partnerships management • Personnel • Sales & Marketing Activities 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subscription based fee 		

Figure 6: Business Model Canvas (updated) for Use Case #2.

Business Model for EFRA		<i>Designed for:</i> Stakeholders in Government		
<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data providers (data vendors, government agencies, or other businesses in related industries) • Technology providers (cloud infrastructure, data storage, data processing, and analytics tools) • Academics & Research organisations • Customer or User Communities (engage for feedback and insights) • Governments and Regulatory Agencies 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Mining and Data Aggregation • Ensure access to data (public and private) • A.I. models training and optimization • Insure efficiency and interoperability of the systems • Summarization (of legal docs) • Retrieval of relevant information • Retrieval-Augmented Generation <p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data sources • Website and online data portal • Data gathering processes • Personalised AI Models • Personnel Expertise • Partner expertise • Efficient Data Structures for Information Management/Address 	<p>Value Propositions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevant industries have significant size, and they are projected to keep growing • Cloud-based platform provides advanced decision-making tools (KER1). • A user-friendly web app that allows discovery and purchase / use of raw data and analytics services (KER2). • A Data Hub enriched with anonymized corporate data sets and supply chain data streams (KER3). • Industry expertise and experience • Summarization of regulatory docs • Personalized retrieval of legal docs • State-of-the-Art solutions for legal docs • AI assisting regulatory data 	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website and online portal • Direct Portal/Customer support • User friendly services through the Marketplace <p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Online customer portal • Social Media • Indirect Sales thought leadership publications (Scientific, Technical, White paper etc.) • Workshops/Webinars • Direct Sales 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governments and Regulatory Agencies • Food Industry Stakeholders • Food Manufacturers & Producers • Agriculture Producers • Testing – Inspection - Certification
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technologies and Intellectual properties development • Online platform’s development and maintenance • Data acquisition and storage costs • Partnerships management • Personnel • Sales & Marketing Activities 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subscription based fee • Project Based pricing 		

Figure 7: Business Model Canvas (updated) for Use Case #3.

Business Model for EFRA		<i>Designed for:</i> Stakeholders in Animal Production		
Key Partners <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Providers (Farmers, Animal owners, government agencies, other related businesses) ● Technology Providers (cloud infrastructure, computational power providers, analytics powerhouse tools, data processors) ● Academia and Research Institutions (Researchers on food safety, data scientists, mycotoxins experts) ● Government bodies and policymakers () 	Key Activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Analyse historical data in search of patterns ● Extract new data from real-world cases ● Train AI models and ensure constant optimisation and update with the latest data ● Ensure efficiency and accuracy of the developed solution 	Value Propositions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Animal husbandry is a growing field, which nevertheless has been slow to adopt new solutions. This has led to inefficiencies which cause reduced production and higher risk. ● Cloud-based analytics platforms offer advanced decision-making tools (KER1) ● Partners have extensive expertise and access to large amounts of data which can be leveraged to train AI models. Specifically for Mycotoxins, samples are analysed monthly to determine concentrations and inform decisions. 	Customer Relationships <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strong presence in industry meetings ● Customer Support ● User-friendly interface in the platform ● Personalised training on platform’s modules 	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ranchers ● Farmers ● Government and regulatory agencies ● Academia ● Research Institutions ● Mycotoxins Researchers
	Key Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data sources ● Public and Private data, always ensuring compliance with regulations ● Personalised AI systems ● Personnel expertise ● Partner expertise 		Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Website ● Customer Portal (web) ● Direct sales in relevant institutions (universities, farms) ● Indirect sales through industry leaders ● Workshops and webinars 	
Cost Structure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Personnel costs ● Data purchase and storage ● Marketing and brand development ● Platform set up and maintenance ● Partnership management 		Revenue Streams <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Subscription model for the platform ● Freemium model for specific segments ● Size/project based pricing ● One-off payments for specific segments ● Dynamic Pricing 		

Figure 8: Business Model Canvas (updated) for Use Case #4.

Business Model for EFRA’s Open access knowledge bas	<i>Designed for:</i> Stakeholders in Food Industry
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<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open access journals • Open access repositories • Technology partners for website hosting 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extension of website’s hosting plan • Continue broadcasting through web-based communication channels (social media) <p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partner Scientific Publications • Partner Technical Publications • Website and online data portal • Social media channels • Partners from other projects 	<p>Value Propositions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help in knowledge diffusion regarding food risk prediction and technology • Help drive innovation in food risk prediction 	<p>User Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media • Email <p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media • Open access journals • Open access repositories 	<p>User Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic & Research organisations • Data Scientists & Analysts • Government & Regulatory Agencies • Food System Stakeholders • Food Safety Experts
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website costs • Personnel costs 		<p>Sustainability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help in safeguarding consumers from foodborne illnesses and hazards • Educate people regarding the use of data and AI in food risk prediction • Drive innovation in the food risk prediction sector 		

Figure 9: Business model Canvas for Non-Commercial results (updated).

8. Intellectual Property Rights Management

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) constitute the legal ownership of creations of the mind, including inventions, designs, names, images, and other innovative outputs, enabling their owners to derive economic or strategic benefit from these assets. Achieving an appropriate balance between the interests of creators and the broader public is essential to stimulate creativity and drive innovation. Within the EFRA project, careful attention is given to the identification and protection of results with potential commercial or industrial value. Where feasible, justified, and strategically relevant, such results are safeguarded through appropriate IPR measures. Detailed explanations of the various forms of IPR protection (patents, copyrights, trademarks, and related mechanisms) are provided in Deliverable D6.2.1.

8.1. IPR Strategies

The EFRA project has delivered substantial research outcomes and technological innovations, necessitating a robust IPR management strategy. This strategy was initially developed and presented in the first iteration of Deliverable 6.2 (D6.2.1), its update (D6.2.2), as well as discussed during the three (3) EFRA IPR workshops. EFRA's approach to IPR management is structured across three complementary levels:

- **During the project:** Priority is given to the identification, protection, and management of IPR generated through project activities. Ownership of IPR is retained by the industry partner that created it, ensuring the potential for subsequent commercial exploitation. To support this, the second IPR workshop was held in Athens during EFRA's plenary meeting, enabling all consortium members to engage in detailed discussions on IPR matters and the exploitation of project results.
- **Knowledge management and dissemination of scientific knowledge:** EFRA is committed to the open dissemination of project results through scientific publications, workshops, seminars, and the project website. This is carried out without imposing restrictions related to intellectual property rights, in full alignment with the Horizon Europe Open Science Policy.
- **Post-project IPR strategy:** RAIN will provide ongoing services to EFRA partners throughout the IPR lifecycle, supporting the protection of project results where such protection is feasible, reasonable, and justified (T6.4). This ensures the long-term safeguarding and strategic use of EFRA's innovations beyond the project's completion.

8.2. Partner obligations

EFRA has followed all IPR management requirements as described in the Grand Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, regarding access rights, ownership of Results, transfer rights, access rights, consequences of non-compliance, and non-disclosure agreements. Detailed elaboration of the can be found in D6.2.1.

8.3. Partners identified background

In accordance with the Grant Agreement, "background" is defined as "*data, know-how, or information (...) that is (...) needed to implement the Action or exploit the results*". In practical terms, background IP refers to any intellectual property that existed prior to the agreement between the project partners. To facilitate project implementation and result exploitation, Access Rights to relevant background IP must generally be granted. Partners are responsible for identifying and mutually agreeing upon the specific background IP applicable to the project. These designations may evolve over time, and the tool for recording background IP has been circulated among partners to allow for updates and additions as deemed necessary. The

background IP identified by EFRA consortium partners, relevant to IPR management, is summarised in the table below (Table 16).

Table 16: Partners identified background and specific restrictions and/or conditions for implementation and exploitation of results

Short name (Country)	Identified Background relevant to IPR	Restrictions
AGROKNOW (GR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agroknow's Data Platform RISKADATA API service and food safety data Agroknow's Intelligence Stack FOODAKAI software 	Copyrighted and protected by IPRs. The described background will be made accessible to project partners for the duration of the project and in the context of and for purposes of specific project tasks.
CNR (IT)	No background added	N/A
SU (SE)	No background added	N/A
WR (NL)	No background added	Background may be used only with the prior consent of WFSR (WR). Data generated outside the project by WFSR (WR) may only be used and published with permission of the WFSR (WR).
JAKALA (IT)	CELLI.analytics : a proprietary platform for text mining and analytics	Proprietary solution protected by IPRs. The background described will be made accessible to project partners for the duration of the project and in the context of and for purposes of specific project tasks.
AGRIVI (HR)	<p>AGRIVI FMS Platform – proprietary software components, data structures, interfaces, and functionalities relevant to agricultural production management.</p> <p>Pest Analysis Modules and Functionalities – including internal procedures, system logic, and methodologies used for collecting, processing, and interpreting pest-related data.</p> <p>Proprietary Pest Detection Algorithms – AGRIVI-developed algorithms, models, and underlying code enabling identification and assessment of pest presence based on multiple input data sources.</p>	Copyrighted and protected by IPRs. The background described will be made accessible to project partners for the duration of the project and in the context of and for purposes of specific project tasks.
RAIN (GR)	No background added	N/A
SGS (RO)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SGS DIGICOMPLY DAAS Platform SGS DIGICOMPLY search engine 	Copyrighted and protected by IPRs. The background described will be made accessible to project partners for the duration of the project and in the context of and for purposes of specific project tasks.
MOY (UK)	No background added	Background may be used only with the prior consent of Moy Park. Data generated outside the project by Moy Park may only be used and published with permission of Moy Park.

8.4. Methodology for defining IPRs and potential disputes

Following the identification and validation of the project’s exploitable results and the corresponding target markets, it is essential to associate the commercial results with the appropriate IPRs. This ensures their correct utilisation, protection, and market distribution. The methodology for defining IPR is fully aligned with the approach used for identifying and characterising EFRA’s KERs. The procedure and associated steps are outlined in the figure below (Figure 10) and provide a structured framework for the systematic management of IPR across the EFRA project.

Figure 10: Inclusion of newly identified IPRs.

For the identification of potential IPRs, the KERs online form (Figure 4) includes a dedicated section to capture this information.

The procedure for addressing potential IPR disputes among EFRA consortium members was detailed in D6.2.1. This procedure outlines the steps to be followed in the event of conflicts arising from the exploitation of one or more commercial results, including notification to the project coordinator and the assessment of any IPR-related conflicts.

As we reach to the end of the project, EFRA results have matured, IPR matters were actively discussed during the third EFRA IPR Workshop (see Section 4.5), held online on **25 November 2025**. Partners were requested to populate the relevant sections of the online tool with details of the results they plan to exploit. For each KER, the characterisation table includes a section where partners provide information on the intended method of protection, such as copyright, trademark, or other appropriate IPR mechanisms (Figure 11).

		<i>If "other", please identify</i>	<i>Other</i>		<i>If "other", please identify</i>	<i>Other</i>
1	EFRA Analytics Powerhouse	Commercial	-	Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts	Copyright	-
2	EFRA Data and Analytics Marketplace: A web application that enables secure and user-friendly trading of datasets and AI models as assets, incorporating encryption and authentication measures	Commercial	-	Academic & Research organisations, Policy makers, Data scientists and data analysts, Food System Stakeholders and Safety Experts	Copyright	-
3	EFRA Data Hub	Commercial	-	Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts	Copyright	-
4	RoBERTa-based web page classifier (part of the EFRA Data Hub): The RoBERTa-based classifier identifies whether web pages are food-related and further categorizes them as either containing food safety incidents or being general opinion pieces or news.	Commercial	-	Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts	Copyright	-
5	Mycotoxins tailor-made AI predictive model and interactive dashboards (part of the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse): The AI model and accompanying dashboards provide customized mycotoxin risk predictions for batches based on country of origin, target mycotoxin, and ingredient, utilizing public lab tests as well as weather and climate data.	Commercial	-	Food companies, Food safety experts and other stakeholders	Copyright	-
6	Mycotoxins occurrence data aggregation and harmonization (part of the EFRA Data Hub): Calibration and customization of Agroknow's data platform to collect, process and harmonize mycotoxins occurrence data in food and feed.	Commercial	-	Food companies, Food safety experts and other stakeholders	Copyright	-
7	Predictions Library (part of the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse): Automates the selection of the best-performing time-series forecasting algorithm for each specific case, based on identified series characteristics, and offers a collection of pre-trained AI models for upstream applications.	Commercial	-	Food companies, Food safety experts and other stakeholders, Data Scientists	Copyright	-
8	Extreme event forecasting (part of EFRA Analytics Powerhouse): The extreme event forecasting AI model calculates the likelihood that a time-series will surpass a set value threshold in the subsequent time step.	Commercial	-	Food companies, Food safety experts and other stakeholders, Data Scientists	Patent	-
9	Intelligent Crawler for Food-Safety Incident Discovery: An Intelligent AI agent crawler automates the discovery, validation, and extraction of food-safety incident data from global public sources.	Commercial	-	Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts	Copyright	-

Figure 11: “KERs Inventory & IPRs” online tool - IPR protection type example

During this period (M25-M36) RAINNO organized the third and final EFRA IPR Workshop, which held online on the 25th of November 2025 (Figure 12), consortium partners were invited to review and confirm both

previously identified and updated IPRs. All feedback, including comments and suggestions, was duly documented, and no objections were raised during the validation process. As a result, the newly identified IPRs were formally endorsed and incorporated into the project's consolidated IPR register. The updated overview of the KERs and their associated IPRs, as of M36, is presented in Table 17.

Table 17: KERs IPR Validation

KER	Partner	IPR
#1 EFRA Analytics Powerhouse	Owner: Jakala, Partners' Contribution: Agroknow, CNR, and SU	Copyright
#2 EFRA Data and Analytics Marketplace	Owner: Agroknow	Copyright
#3 EFRA Data Hub	Owner: Jakala, Partners' Contribution: Agroknow, WFSR, and SU	Copyright
#4 RoBERTa-based web page classifier	Owner: Agroknow	Copyright
#5 Mycotoxins tailor-made AI predictive model and interactive dashboards	Owner: Agroknow	Copyright
#6 Mycotoxins occurrence data aggregation and harmonization	Owner: Agroknow	Copyright
#7 Predictions Library	Owner: Agroknow	Copyright
#8 Extreme event forecasting	Owner: Agroknow	Copyright
#9 Intelligent Crawler for Food-Safety Incident Discovery	Owner: Agroknow	Copyright

8.5. IPR Workshops: Background and Foreground Knowledge

The EFRA project has established and implemented a comprehensive IPR management scheme, supported by a series of three dedicated IPR workshops. These workshops were designed to systematically identify relevant background and foreground intellectual property, clarify ownership arrangements, and ensure the effective screening, management, and protection of any new IP generated throughout the project. All three

IPR workshops have been successfully delivered by RAINNO during the three years of the project, with the objective of providing consortium partners with a clear and shared understanding of the IPR framework, processes, and responsibilities.

The workshops focus on three key areas:

1. **IPR Protection Strategies:** Participants explore the most suitable protection strategies, including patents, copyrights, and trade secrets, to safeguard project outcomes such as software, datasets, and creative deliverables. For instance, results like the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse and the Mycotoxins AI predictive model have been identified as being protected by copyright.
2. **IPR Procedures:** The workshops guide participants through formal procedures for identifying and documenting new IP, ensuring each item is correctly linked to the process for defining Key Exploitable Results (KERs).
3. **Exploitation Alignment:** Finally, the sessions help partners align on how project results will be used or commercialized. This includes defining agreements, exploring (non)commercial synergies, and using tools such as the BFMULO Matrix to record partners' intentions regarding Results (Foreground) IP and specific exploitation routes.

The first and the second workshops are being described in previous the previous deliverables (D6.2.1 and D6.2.2). The third and final EFRA IPR workshop was held on 25 November 2025 and was delivered in an online format. This interactive session focused on the practical implementation of the EFRA IPR management framework and associated procedures. Emphasis was placed on the identification and management of KERs and on clarifying single and joint ownership arrangements. The workshop facilitated structured and collaborative discussions among consortium members to ensure alignment on ownership, exploitation pathways, and future use of project outcomes.

The workshop agenda was carefully structured to address the key dimensions of IPR management within EFRA. It commenced with an overview of core concepts related to Intellectual Property (IP) and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), followed by a detailed presentation of EFRA-specific IP management workflows and best practices. A dedicated session reviewed the KERs Matrix, supporting the assessment of ownership models and exploitation intentions for each KER. In-depth discussions on single versus joint ownership were held to ensure a shared understanding of rights and obligations associated with the exploitation of EFRA results.

Key discussion topics included:

- **IPR Strategy Refresher: Background vs. Foreground:** Quick overview of the sound IPR management scheme. Revisit the definitions of Background (IP brought to the project) and Foreground (results generated by the project partners).
- **Foreground IP Identification and Protection:** Discussions centred on the process by which each partner examines the possibility of protecting the results generated during the project, as well as a review of the requirements for protecting those results when protection is possible and justified.
- **Final KERs Catalogue and IPR Validation:** Review of the final catalogue of KERs and their corresponding IPR status (e.g., Copyright, TO BE DECIDED).
- **Accelerating Exploitation:** Finalization of agreements on the exploitation of results, the definition of commercial and non-commercial synergies with potential partners and collaborators, and a review of the BFMULO Matrix intentions.
- **Post-Project IPR Strategy and Sustainability:** Discussion on the whole IPR lifecycle concerning appropriate protection of results post-project. Reviewing the commitment for exploitation up to four years after the end of the action.

The workshop promoted an open and collaborative atmosphere that allowed partners to exchange perspectives and align on a clear and unified approach to IPR management. It highlighted the strategic value of strong IP governance in protecting EFRA's innovations and enhancing their exploitation potential. After the workshop, all relevant materials, including presentations and templates, were distributed to the consortium. Overall, the final IPR workshop concentrated on foreground IP, supporting partners in evaluating and, where appropriate, protecting the results generated throughout the project.

The screenshot shows a Zoom meeting interface. On the left, a presentation slide titled "PURPOSE OF FINAL IPR WORKSHOP" is displayed. The slide features the EFRA logo and three main sections:

- Core Objective:** The final IPR workshop in EFRA is dedicated to results (foreground) IP generated during the project. It guides partners in deciding whether to protect their results, how to protect them, and under what conditions, ensuring long-term value capture.
- Horizon Europe Context:** This workshop aligns with Horizon Europe's emphasis on protecting innovative results while respecting open-science obligations. It ensures that EFRA's outcomes are sustainable and compliant with EU funding requirements.
- Consortium Alignment:** The workshop fosters collaboration among consortium members, ensuring that all partners are aligned on the protection and exploitation strategies for foreground IP, minimizing future disputes.

The slide also includes the website "efraproject.eu" and the number "13". On the right side of the Zoom window, a grid of video feeds shows several participants, including Salvoire Trani, Ali Hurreyetoğlu, Anna Romanova, and Terzi Gouthas, along with a blue network diagram icon.

Figure 12: The 3rd (final) EFRA IPR Workshop.

9. Next Steps

The previous iterations of this deliverable (D6.2.1 and D6.2.2) established a methodical roadmap for maturing EFRA's exploitation framework, business models, and sustainability plan, with D6.2.3 identified as the definitive milestone where these elements would converge into a complete, implementation-ready toolset. With all four use cases now validated under real operational conditions, the KER portfolio expanded to 9 mature assets, and the transition to the DSSC collaborative business model framework successfully completed, the project has achieved the strategic inflection point at which the focus shifts decisively from planning and iteration to disciplined, resource-backed execution of the post-project commitments detailed throughout this final deliverable.

As the concluding IPR and Sustainability Report for the EFRA project, D6.2.3 wraps up the complete lifecycle of strategic development work under WP6, providing partners with the definitive reference package (including finalised KER catalogue, BFMULO exploitation matrix, business model canvases reflecting real-world validation feedback, IPR protection timelines, and four-year sustainability roadmap) for immediate operationalisation from January 2026 onwards. The timing is strategically significant: the Horizon Europe Work Programme 2026-2027, with its emphasis on deployment readiness, market-ready business cases, and food system transformation aligned with the Farm to Fork Strategy, creates immediate opportunity windows for successor initiatives that can leverage EFRA as mature building blocks.

In concrete operational terms, the next steps are structured in three phases over the first 18 months post-project:

- i. **Phase 1 (Q1–Q2 2026)** focuses on formalising the EFRA Platform governance structure: designating exploitation leads per KER, establishing the Platform Steering Committee comprising partner representatives and external advisors, executing bilateral and multilateral exploitation and data-sharing agreements, and operationalising the four-year sustainability roadmap with detailed quarterly milestones and KPI targets.
- ii. **Phase 2 (Q2–Q3 2026)** concentrates on market-facing activation: launching the EFRA Data & Analytics Marketplace with initial paying subscribers, deploying federated learning workflows with pilot food industry partners, and mobilising the first cohort of licensing agreements for proprietary AI models with academic and commercial entities.
- iii. **Phase 3 (Q3–Q4 2026)** anticipates the pipeline of successor proposals: EFRA partners will initiate joint applications under Horizon Europe Cluster 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture & Environment) thematic calls, Digital Europe Programme common data space initiatives, and targeted national innovation schemes that explicitly build on EFRA assets as technical and organisational foundations. These successor proposals will ensure continuity of platform development, offset early operating costs during the scale-up phase, and signal to the market that EFRA represents durable, EU-backed innovation infrastructure rather than time-limited research output.

Throughout all phases, EFRA will maintain structured engagement with the EFSA Strategy 2027 implementation agenda, particularly regarding EFSA's published priorities for AI, data mining, interoperable digital platforms, and standardised data formats for regulatory submission and assessment. This alignment positions EFRA not as a standalone tool but as an operational instantiation of EFSA's own digital transformation roadmap, thereby strengthening adoption prospects within the regulatory community and supporting EFSA's legislative reform process under the amended General Food Law.

10. Conclusions

This final iteration of the **"Integrated toolset for multiplying impact"** represents the comprehensive synthesis and authoritative closure of all conceptual, methodological, and practical contributions developed across D6.2.1, D6.2.2, and the full project duration, confirming EFRA's successful transition from research prototype to exploitation-ready innovation platform embedded within the European data ecosystem. Rather than duplicating the detailed technical descriptions, market analyses, or preliminary frameworks already validated in previous versions, D6.2.3 serves as an update and the conclusive IPR and Sustainability Report for the entire EFRA project, delivering the finalised eight-KER portfolio with associated IPR protections, consolidated BFMULO exploitation matrix, business model canvases refined through real-world piloting feedback, operational governance templates, and structured four-year post-project sustainability roadmap with specified funding sources, revenue targets and contingency mechanisms, which collectively fulfil all WP6 objectives and Horizon Europe impact requirements.

By integrating lessons from operational validation across industry partners (MOY Park, AGRIVI, SGS Romania) and academic institutions with strategic alignment to EFSA's digitalisation priorities, the Farm to Fork Strategy implementation agenda, and the EU's accelerating investment in trustworthy data spaces and common data environments, this deliverable confirms that EFRA has achieved full maturity and operational readiness. The project now possesses all organisational, technical, legal, and financial foundations required for sustained operation and impact generation within Europe's evolving food safety and data ecosystems beyond the formal project lifetime. The KER portfolio, spanning predictive risk analytics, automated compliance tools, curated data infrastructure, and federated learning architectures, addresses concrete, validated user needs across the food supply chain, with business models demonstrating revenue viability across multiple stakeholder segments and sustainable funding pathways combining commercial subscriptions, licensing, and strategic project-based funding.

Critically, EFRA's durability depends not only on technological maturity but on strategic ecosystem positioning. By aligning the platform with EFSA's published digital transformation agenda, the Common European Data Spaces framework, and the deployment-focused priorities of Horizon Europe 2026-2027, EFRA partners have de-risked the sustainability model and positioned the project outcomes as essential infrastructure for EU food safety resilience and digital governance rather than as optional tools. The four-year roadmap, combined with the exploitation pipeline formalised across all nine consortium partners, provides concrete assurance that EFRA will continue to generate measurable value, including reduced food safety incidents, accelerated regulatory compliance, strengthened supply chain transparency, and contribution to European data sovereignty, well into the 2030s. The transition from Horizon Europe grant funding to self-sustaining platform operations is neither automatic nor guaranteed. However, the strategic choices embedded in this deliverable (i.e. the collaborative business model, the diversified KER portfolio, the alignment with regulatory and policy ecosystems, and the structured partnership commitments) maximise the likelihood that EFRA will evolve into a recognisable, trusted institution within European food systems innovation rather than fade as a time-limited research output.

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